

Survey Guidelines for Monitoring Threatened Species

*Towards monitoring standards compatible with the
Ecological Monitoring System of Australia*

Citation

O'Neill S, Laws M, Finlayson T, Kilpatrick E, Steen C, and Sparrow B (2025) Survey Guidelines for Monitoring Threatened Species: Towards monitoring standards compatible with the Ecological Monitoring System Australia. Report to the Australian Government. TERN, Adelaide.

Version

Version 1

Last updated: 4 December 2025

Acknowledgements and contributors

This publication is the result of a body of work funded by the Australian Government Department of Climate Change, Energy, the Environment and Water to develop standardised ecological monitoring standards.

TERN is funded by the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy.

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Version control

The version history of this document is identified below. Enquiries regarding version control should be directed to tern@adelaide.edu.au

Version	Date	Version update overview
1	4 December 2025	First public release

Summary of key recommendations

This document sets out key recommendations for monitoring threatened species populations. Species-specific recommendations are provided for 25 species (six birds, three frogs, nine mammals, two reptiles and five plants). These species-specific recommendations identify best-practice methods based on the recommendations of the species experts, which are based on successful monitoring methods conducted in the past (enabling comparisons) and what current best-practices are considered most suitable. Over time, as technologies improve and innovative techniques evolve, the best-practice methods will likely be updated.

In addition to the species-specific recommendations outlined, general information is provided that can be applied to monitoring all species, regardless of conservation status. If utilising modules of the Ecological Monitoring System of Australia (EMSA), and especially if using the associated EMSA app Monitor, the general recommendations are already built into the design, workflows, and standards of EMSA.

For all monitoring, the following recommendations should be applied.

1. **Refer to the existing literature to understand the target species** distribution and habitat requirements, biology, and how to distinguish the species from other similar species. For fauna species, also understand the food and refuge requirements, including home ranges, breeding and movements. Available resources include the *Monitoring Priority Threatened Species* series, which includes literature overviews for 70 species and literature reviews for 40 species (see Appendix 1 for a list of species for which literature reviews are available).
2. **Refer to available existing species-specific survey guidelines**, such as the recommendations set out in Section 4. Table 1 identifies which species are covered in this document.
3. **Refer to other species-specific survey guidelines**, such as the 2010-2011 series: *Survey guidelines for Australia's threatened birds* DEWHA (2010a), *Australia's threatened frogs* DEWHA (2010b), *Australia's threatened mammals* (DSEWPC 2011a), and *Australia's threatened reptiles* (DSEWPC 2011b). See Appendix 2 for a list of species included in these documents.
4. **Refer to relevant threatened species recovery teams or lead agencies** undertaking monitoring and seek current best-practice recommendations and guidelines. For the species included in the *Monitoring Priority Threatened Species* series, the literature reviews identify key agencies and organisations involved in species-specific research and recovery.
5. **Record accurate details of the monitoring undertaken, and refer to the modules of the Ecological Monitoring System of Australia (ESMA) for guidance.** Whilst the EMSA modules do not specifically provide species-specific guidance, they do cover a broad range of monitoring techniques that have been both standardised in the way in which they are conducted (i.e. the field implementation techniques) and how data is collected following these techniques. Appendix 3 provides an overview of the EMSA modules. Appendix 4 provides a list of survey information that should be recorded as a minimum.
6. **Ensure data and information are reusable by having associated metadata accurately recorded, and utilise existing standards to document monitoring undertaken and record results.** Existing standards, such as the Australian Biodiversity Information Standards (ABIS), should be used and maintained. Making data accessible enables better use and re-use of data.
7. **Ensure data and information are accessible and discoverable in shared repositories**, such as the Australian Government's Biodiversity Data Repository, under the least restrictive conditions possible (preferably Creative Commons No Rights Reserved). Such repositories have carefully managed data privacy standards.

8. **Analyse results and ensure data is fit for purpose and meets the specific needs for how the information is being used to inform decision-making and management actions.**
9. **Contribute to the Threatened Species Index and related systems for tracking species trajectories.** The Threatened Species Index (TSX), managed by TERN, provides reliable and robust measures of change in the relative abundance of Australia's threatened and near-threatened species at national, state and regional levels. Understanding these changes in species populations is critical for monitoring progress towards Australia's conservation targets. Moreover, the TSX allows users to measure and report on the benefits of conservation investments, as well as justify and design targeted responses and raise the profile of threatened species.
10. **Ecological practitioners should be committed to contributing meaningful, science-backed, fit-for-purpose data to contribute to evidence-based decision-making.** Effective monitoring and management of threatened species relies on industry-wide commitment to using best-practice, species-specific (where available) methods to collect meaningful data. These monitoring standards have been developed through expert input and historical success, and as monitoring technologies evolve, so too must our approaches. General principles, such as reviewing existing literature, using survey guidelines, applying standardised methods via EMSA, and publishing data to national repositories, help ensure consistency, accuracy, and long-term impact across species and ecosystems. Every datapoint collected contributes to a clearer picture of biodiversity health, guiding conservation efforts, informing robust and evidence-based decision-making and shaping policy.

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1 Introduction

The *Survey Guidelines for Monitoring Threatened Species* project, a collaboration of the Department of Climate Change, Energy, the Environment, and Water (DCCEEW) and the Terrestrial Ecosystem Research Network (TERN), aims to improve our knowledge of threatened species by enhancing accessibility and sharing of quality scientific threatened species data. By developing best practice field survey guidelines and recommendations, practitioners will be better equipped to conduct standardised, repeatable surveys.

By identifying the monitoring methods typically implemented by practitioners, documenting and assessing the techniques known to work, and identifying opportunities to standardise the methods, we can move towards ensuring all monitoring is species-appropriate, comparable between practitioners and populations, and repeatable over time. Further, together with consistent terminology, guidelines, instructions, and data collection, we can refine efforts and resources to measure and share information. Data collected using robust, standardised methods will improve our knowledge of threatened species and underpin threatened species recovery at scale. This project is essential to establishing monitoring protocols and data repositories to enhance the accessibility and sharing of threatened species data.

The *Threatened Species Action Plan 2022-2032* identifies 22 targets. Target 20 states "Monitoring standards for all priority species are published and monitoring tools and protocols are created for at least 50 per cent of priority species". Related to this target are the following actions:

- Identify best practice monitoring protocols for all priority species
- Develop and publish standardised monitoring tools and protocols for at least 50 per cent of priority species.

This document, together with the *Monitoring Priority Threatened Species* series, which includes literature reviews of existing monitoring methods for 11 priority bird species, 12 priority mammal species, 3 priority invertebrate species, 1 priority fish species, 5 priority reptile species, 3 priority frog species, and 5 priority plant species, and 70 literature overviews of priority species, aims to in part achieve Target 20, and identify best practice monitoring protocols for all priority species, and identify standardised tools suitable for many of the 110 priority species.

This document outlines recommendations for the minimum data-related information to record when conducting monitoring surveys for priority threatened species. Information is recorded to document:

- site location, including the context of the wider project area, surrounding land uses and land tenure
- habitat of the site, including vegetation composition and structure attributes, soil and rock substrate, refuges and resource availability
- condition of the site, including historical and current disturbances, as well as ongoing disturbances related to development activities
- timing of the surveys, and the survey effort undertaken
- skills and experience of the survey personnel
- specific monitoring methods, techniques, and equipment used
- results of the monitoring
- data access and availability, and data custodian contact details, specifically where researchers or anyone interested in the data can find the dataset.

A key aim of this document is to promote the recommendation that all ecological practitioners conduct surveys for threatened species using best-practice survey methods that are appropriate for the species of interest. Where species-specific methods and recommendations are limited, the principles outlined in the first section of this document should serve as a general guideline.

It is essential to recognise that the recommendations outlined in this document are designed to identify best practices. However, they are not mandatory.

1.1 Types of monitoring

1.1.1 Presence

Presence is the detection of a species in a particular area at a given time. Confirmation of a species can assist with the identification of critical habitat and guide targeted surveys or conservation efforts.

Occupancy is the proportion of surveyed sites or areas within a landscape where a species is known or estimated to occur. Occupancy provides a broad measure of how widely a species is distributed, which is crucial for tracking the contraction or expansion of a species' range over time.

1.1.2 Absence and non-detection

Non-detection reflects when a species has not been detected in a specified area at a particular time. However, non-detection does not necessarily indicate that a species is truly absent – i.e. it may not have been detected due to other factors such as limited survey effort, inappropriate survey techniques, environmental conditions or low numbers.

To be confident that a species is truly absent, a significant survey effort, including at optimal conditions, is required for an extended duration.

1.1.3 Abundance and density

Abundance is the total number of individuals of a species in a defined area or population. Where population estimates are difficult to obtain (e.g., low capture rates or insufficient data), the minimum number known alive (MNKA) can also be used as a simple population index that represents the lowest possible number of individuals known to be alive in a population at a specific time. Density is the number of individuals per unit area (e.g., individuals per hectare). Evaluating density can better facilitate comparisons across different sites or periods. Both abundance and density measures are important for assessing the status of a species population to identify trends that may signal recovery or further decline.

1.1.4 Population demographics, survivorship and longevity

Population demographics identify the characteristics of a population, such as age structure, sex ratio, and reproductive rates. Survivorship is the proportion of individuals surviving from one life stage to another, while longevity is the typical or maximum lifespan of an individual under natural conditions. These features provide insight into population viability and are important considerations for species management. For instance, low survivorship may indicate immediate conservation or intervention is required, while long-lived species may be slower to recover from population declines, highlighting the need for long-term planning.

1.1.5 Habitat and habitat condition

Habitat is the physical and biological environment where an organism, species or population lives. Suitable habitat for a species revolves around adequate resource availability such as food, refuges and attributes important for breeding. Habitat condition is a measure of the ecological integrity or

quality of a habitat, often described in relation to degradation, fragmentation, or ecological function.

1.1.6 Threats and disturbances

Threats are ongoing or emerging external pressures or processes that negatively impact a species, population or ecosystem, such as invasive species, land clearing, altered fire regimes, or climate change. Disturbance is a temporary or recurring event that results in a pronounced change in an ecosystem, community or population. Disturbances can be natural or human-induced and include incidents of fire, flood, drought, or human activities like logging. Monitoring disturbance provides an indication of the resilience of a species or habitat, while identifying and mitigating threats are important for informing why a species is declining and therefore guide recovery actions.

1.1.7 Impact assessment

A formal process to evaluate how a proposed action (e.g., infrastructure development, mining) could affect a species, its habitat or associated ecological processes. Accurate impact assessments promote informed decisions that balance the need for development with conservation responsibilities.

1.2 Tracking species trajectories with the Threatened Species Index

The Threatened Species Index (TSX) is a tool designed to help understand changes to Australia's threatened species over time. The TSX provides reliable and robust measures of change in the relative abundance of Australia's threatened and near-threatened species at national, state and regional levels.

Understanding these changes in species populations is crucial for monitoring progress towards Australia's conservation targets. Moreover, the TSX allows users to measure and report on the benefits of conservation investments, as well as justify and design targeted responses and raise the profile of threatened species.

It is recommended that all threatened species monitoring is conducted in a way that enables data to be provided to the TSX.

In order for your data to be used as a time series for the Threatened Species Index, it must:

- Be collected at the same specific place each time, not in a general region, e.g. 'Sherwood Arboretum' is acceptable, 'Brisbane' is not.
- Have full resolution coordinates (e.g. a latitude and longitude) with a specified datum/projection e.g. WGS84
- Be collected in at least two different years.
- Contain information on the year the survey was undertaken. However, month and date is also helpful for seasonal comparisons if that information is available.
- Specify the species and (if applicable) the subspecies that was surveyed.
- Specify what you counted (e.g. nests) and have a count, e.g. 50.
- Be collected with the same method each time. Metadata on effort, such as survey duration and size of area surveyed, is also important so that we can compare 'apples with apples'.

1.2.1 Maximising the usefulness of monitoring data

The key ways to maximise the usefulness of monitoring data are to:

- Be consistent. Don't change survey methods/protocols. Survey in the same season/month each time, especially when this is influential. For example, Far Eastern Curlew numbers have been increasing in Darwin Harbour over the last decade, but a shift in the survey timing (to winter, for example) could completely undermine the trend data, as Far Eastern Curlews are migratory and only present in Australia at particular times of year.
- Decide what you are counting. Choose the unit of measurement you use and stick to it. Examples include counts of breeding pairs, nests or individuals, trapping rates, densities of individuals (counts over fixed areas/transects) or occupancy rate (no. of presences / no. of absences).
- Monitor for the long term. Although a time series can be as short as two years, this is an extremely short timeframe. The longer you monitor a site, and the more consistently it is surveyed, the greater the ability to detect change. Note that monitoring sites every year is preferable; however, the TSX can include time-series with missed years, which commonly occurs in ecological monitoring (due to gaps in finances, fieldworker availability or even something as mundane as a vehicle breakdown on the way to a site one year!).
- Add to the existing time series. Why start a new time series from year zero if someone around the corner has been surveying a site for 10 years already? Find out if you can help to keep their monitoring going, replicating their method to ensure consistency in survey effort and methodology.
- Record true absences of species. Zero counts are just as important in ecological data as non-zero counts. If absences or non-detections of a species are not recorded, then trend estimates may be significantly biased.
- Collect representative data. Try to sample sites across the entire species range, but don't try to do too much. You don't need to count every individual every year to get a reliable population trend.

1.3 Existing survey guidelines

The following published guidelines have been consulted in the development of this document, and should be reviewed when developing threatened species monitoring efforts:

- Survey guidelines for Australia's threatened birds
 - DEWHA (2010) Survey guidelines for Australia's threatened birds. Guidelines for detecting birds listed as threatened under the Environment Protection and Biodiversity Conservation Act 1999, Department of the Environment, Water, Heritage and the Arts, Canberra.
- Survey guidelines for Australia's threatened frogs
 - DEWHA (2010) Survey guidelines for Australia's threatened frogs. Guidelines for detecting frogs listed as threatened under the Environment Protection and Biodiversity Conservation Act 1999. Department of the Environment, Water, Heritage and the Arts, Canberra, ACT.
- Survey guidelines for Australia's threatened mammals
 - DSEWPC (2011) Survey guidelines for Australia's threatened mammals: Guidelines for detecting mammals listed as threatened under the Environment Protection and Biodiversity Conservation Act 1999. Australian Government; Department of

Sustainability, Environment, Water, Population and Communities, Canberra, ACT.

- Survey guidelines for Australia's threatened reptiles
 - DSEWPC (2011) Survey guidelines for Australia's threatened reptiles. Guidelines for detecting reptiles listed as threatened under the Environment Protection and Biodiversity Conservation Act 1999. Australian Government; Department of Sustainability, Environment, Water, Population and Communities, Canberra, ACT.

This document contains species-specific survey guidelines for 25 of the 110 Priority Threatened Species (see Table 1). The 25 species were selected after an assessment of the species most in need of standardised monitoring survey methods. Some of the species were included because no other species-specific guidelines exist, whilst others were selected because multiple restoration projects are monitoring the species (or looking to monitor the species in the near future) and therefore identifying monitoring guidelines was considered highly important to identify as soon as possible, so there was some commonality across the projects.

Table 1. List of species for which species-specific survey guidelines have been prepared.

Species	Scientific name	EPBC conservation status	Species-specific profile in the Survey Guidelines for Australia's threatened birds / mammals / reptiles	Species-specific guidelines – this document
Birds				
Australasian Bittern	<i>Botaurus poiciloptilus</i>	Endangered	No	Yes see 4.1.1
Eastern Curlew	<i>Numenius madagascariensis</i>	Critically Endangered	No	Yes see 4.1.2
Hooded Plover (eastern)	<i>Thinornis cucullatus cucullatus</i>	Vulnerable	No	Yes see 4.1.3
King Island Scrubtit	<i>Acanthornis magna greeniana</i>	Endangered	Yes	Yes see 4.1.4
Noisy Scrub-bird	<i>Atrichornis clamosus</i>	Endangered	No	Yes see 4.1.5
Plains-wanderer	<i>Pedionomus torquatus</i>	Critically Endangered	Yes	Yes see 4.1.6
Frogs				
Southern Bell Frog	<i>Litoria raniformis</i>	Vulnerable	Yes	Yes see 4.2.1
Mountain Frog	<i>Philoria kundagungan</i>	Endangered	No	Yes see 4.2.2
Mountain-top Nursery Frog	<i>Cophixalus monticola</i>	Critically Endangered	No	Yes see 4.2.3
Mammals				
Brush-tailed Rock-wallaby	<i>Petrogale penicillata</i>	Vulnerable	Yes	Yes see 4.4.1
Chuditch, Western Quoll	<i>Dasyurus geoffroi</i>	Vulnerable	Yes	Yes see 4.4.2
Eastern Quoll, Luaner	<i>Dasyurus viverrinus</i>	Endangered	No	Yes see 4.4.3
Northern Quoll	<i>Dasyurus hallucatus</i>	Endangered	Yes	Yes see 4.4.4
Greater Bilby	<i>Macrotis lagotis</i>	Vulnerable	Yes	Yes see 4.4.5
New Holland Mouse, Pookila	<i>Pseudomys novaehollandiae</i>	Vulnerable	No	Yes see 4.4.6
Numbat	<i>Myrmecobius fasciatus</i>	Endangered	Yes	Yes see 4.4.7
Southern Bent-wing Bat	<i>Miniopterus orianae bassanii</i>	Critically Endangered	No	Yes see 4.4.8
Western Ringtail Possum	<i>Pseudocheirus occidentalis</i>	Critically Endangered	Yes	Yes see 4.4.9
Reptiles				
Arnhem Land Gorges Skink	<i>Bellatorias obiri</i>	Endangered	Yes	Yes see 4.5.1
Great Desert Skink, Tjakura, Warrarna, Mulyamiji	<i>Liopholis kintorei</i>	Vulnerable	Yes	Yes see 4.5.2
Plants				
Adamson's Blown-grass	<i>Lachnagrostis adamsonii</i>	Endangered	NA	Yes see 4.6.1
King Blue-grass	<i>Dichanthium queenslandicum</i>	Endangered	NA	Yes see 4.6.2
Native Guava	<i>Rhodomyrtus psidioides</i>	Critically Endangered	NA	Yes see 4.6.3
Stiff Groundsel	<i>Senecio behrianus</i>	Endangered	NA	Yes see 4.6.4
Waddy-wood, Waddy	<i>Acacia peuce</i>	Vulnerable	NA	Yes see 4.6.5

1.5 EMSA survey protocols

The Ecological Monitoring System of Australia (EMSA) has been designed to establish a standardised method for conducting ecological monitoring surveys. EMSA contains a range of modules (23 with more in development) that cover many different groups of related ecological attributes. The EMSA modules include:

- On-plot modules, to be conducted in 1 ha (100 x 100 m) monitoring plots
 - Plot Layout and Selection Module
 - Plot Description Module
 - Photopoints Module
 - Floristics Module
 - Plant Tissue Vouchering Module
 - Cover Module
 - Basal Area Module
 - Coarse Woody Debris Module
 - Fire Severity Module
 - Recruitment Module
 - Condition Module
 - Soils Module
 - Vertebrate Fauna Module
 - Invertebrate Fauna Module.

- Off-plot modules, which can be conducted within the study area, but not restricted to 1 ha monitoring plots:
 - [Vegetation Mapping Module](#)
 - [Opportune Module](#)
 - [Camera Trapping Module](#)
 - [Fauna Aerial Surveys Module](#)
 - [Fauna Ground Counts Module](#)
 - [Herbivory and Physical Damage Module](#)
 - [Pest Fauna Control Activities Module](#)
 - [Sign-based Fauna Surveys Module](#)
 - [Targeted Surveys Module.](#)

Each module contains sufficient background information to justify the selection of methods that the module focuses on. Each module may contain multiple protocols, whereby the user can select the protocol that best suits their specific project and monitoring needs, which can be based on the level of data intensity required, as well as the specific methods to suit the project's desired outcomes.

Surveyors in the field use a field data collection web-app, called Monitor, to collect data in the field, negating the need for post-survey data entry. The app is designed for optimal survey workflow, allow surveyors to collect and transmit standardised information tied to controlled vocabularies and definitions straight from the field. The app has many layers of checks in place to ensure data is restricted to controlled ranges, thereby reducing the chance of data entry errors.

Data collected using Monitor is sent to the Australian Government's Biodiversity Data Repository (BDR), enabling data sharing and better re-use of valuable monitoring data. Data entered into the BDR may be used to assess the trajectories of Australia's environment and biodiversity and inform future management actions.

Whilst the EMSA modules have been designed for in-field data entry using Monitor, the instruction manuals are invaluable resources to aid in designing ecological monitoring programs of all kinds, including monitoring of threatened species.

Throughout this document, where appropriate, the relevant EMSA Modules are identified and highlighted as a resource to consider reviewing.

The Australian Government and TERN are continuing to explore opportunities to develop EMSA and are working on a range of visualisation and analysis tools for EMSA data. If you would like more information or would like to be involved, please contact the Long-term Monitoring team (ltmp@dcceew.gov.au) or TERN (emsa_support@adelaide.edu.au) for more information.

2 General guidelines applicable to all monitoring

2.1 Permits, licences and land permissions

Before any on-ground monitoring effort commences, ensure the correct permits, ethics, and land permissions have been obtained before surveying.

Any monitoring that involves the disturbance to wildlife will require compliance with the *Australian code for the care and use of animals for scientific purposes* (the Code).

Wildlife ethics applications will require careful consideration of many aspects of planning fauna surveys, including:

- When not to survey and appropriate timing of surveys (time of year, avoiding breeding and dispersal periods)
- What survey methods and techniques are appropriate
- Minimising disturbance, including not excavating refuges (i.e. burrows, bark, hides under rocks) unless necessary
- The requirement to exercise caution for all disturbances the survey effort may cause, particularly towards disturbance-sensitive species
- The requirement to minimise animal handling and carefully plan all activities to minimise the time animals are being held in traps
- The requirement to follow best-practice hygiene and biosecurity practices to minimise risks. It is important to consult with relevant jurisdictions to identify requirements and liaise with local area experts for local knowledge of biosecurity threats, including phytophthora, plant pathogens and Chytrid fungus.

Once permits and licences have been obtained, ensure all relevant information is documented and conditions are understood. Record:

- Issuing authority
- Permit name
- Permit holder name
- Permit number
- Permit start date
- Permit expiry date
- Specified location information
- Contact details of the landholder/manager, with documented approval.

When publishing results, certain aspects of a project must also be declared. For example, scientific publications commonly require a section at the end of a paper outlining key project details such as:

- acknowledgement of project partners, funding bodies and individuals or organisations who provided in-kind support
- ethical considerations, including the ethics approval number and the approval committee
- permitting information such as scientific permit numbers and the issuing body

- data availability statement – whether data are available, and if so, where they can be accessed. Accessible data should include all authors, year of publication, title of dataset, record ID, publisher/repository name, DOI/ URL link or reference number. If data are not available online or in supplementary material, information on how the data can be obtained should be included instead (e.g. data will be shared upon reasonable request with permission from [third party] or corresponding author). Otherwise, it should be clearly specified that data cannot be shared due to ethical or privacy reasons.

This information enhances transparency, supports reproducibility and ensures recognition and accountability across all aspects of the project. It also promotes responsible data use and helps meet ethical, legal and institutional requirements.

2.2 Desktop reviews and survey planning guidelines

2.2.1 Planning for initial visits and reconnaissance surveys

Reconnaissance surveys are important to conduct to help the surveyors understand the environment, including the habitats present and their condition. Reconnaissance surveys are also used to help plan the monitoring surveys and inform logistical considerations for moving around the survey area. Reconnaissance surveys inform the design of monitoring programs, as they help define the boundary of areas to survey based on the presence of suitable habitat, prioritise the important areas, and inform optimal survey effort to cover the survey area adequately.

Conduct a reconnaissance survey to:

- Determine the vegetation communities present – do they match the habitat requirements of the species of interest?
- Assess the condition of the vegetation communities present - do they match the habitat requirements of the species of interest?
- Determine if the habitats are suitable – Are habitats and microhabitats that the species of interest requires present in the area?
- Determine if all areas of interest within the survey area are accessible. Meet with, or liaise with, land managers to discuss access requirements and identify any areas to avoid, or specific requirements to meet
- Take photographs and record capture site and access information, ideally using mapping software
- Record opportunistic observations
- Ground truth any mapped vegetation units and ensure mapping is accurate
- Record potential survey areas that meet the habitat requirements of the target species
- Visit any target locations, including any sites of historical records
- Practice key survey methods, and record test data
- Record opportune observations (both to capture species presence, test recording methods, and commence data collection). Recording opportune observations during initial visits can also be a way of testing data capture methods, particularly if using tablets and software, as it enables the software and hardware to be tested in the field before the survey begins.

Planning for initial visits should consider:

- Identifying and prioritising visits during the optimum time of year for the target species – noting multiple visits at different times of the year may be required
- Scheduling commitments and availability of the survey team, and the surveyors most suitable to conduct the work
- The time needed to adequately complete the tasks required
- Prioritising species with defined survey windows (i.e. flowering times of plant species to improve detectability)
- Prioritising habitats (vegetation communities, landscape position, soils, condition and disturbance values, etc) that most suit the species of interest
- Logistics and site access requirements
- Equipment needs and survey set-up, and disturbances associated with the set-up for the actual survey. This is particularly important to plan during initial visits prior to fauna trapping surveys as establishing traps (i.e. pitfall traps requiring digging of pitfalls into the ground) creates significant disturbance. It is not ideal to be establishing pitfall traps at the most optimal time of year, and the set-up should be conducted prior.

2.2.2 Post-reconnaissance review

After reconnaissance surveys and initial visits have been completed, review the information gathered to:

- Review and refine the understanding of the project site, particularly the habitats, vegetation communities, species composition, and condition values
- Re-assess the likelihood of the target species being present based on the new information obtained and a better understanding of the habitats, condition and disturbances
- Select the sites to be surveyed
- Prioritise the survey sites, identifying the areas most likely of supporting the target species, and dedicate the most survey effort to these areas
- Identify any areas to completely rule out, or at least give lowest survey effort priority to
- Plan all aspects of the surveys required.

2.3 Documenting the monitoring undertaken

During and after the surveys have been completed, ensure records are kept up to date. Provide a summary of the type of monitoring being undertaken. The EMSA Targeted Surveys Module can provide some guidance. Record:

- Overview of the monitoring type, e.g. flora monitoring, fauna monitoring, habitat condition, ecological community assessment, ecological community condition, or land/soil monitoring
- Overview of the monitoring scale, e.g. state-wide, NRM region, IBRA region, IBRA sub-region, site
- Landscape of the monitoring, e.g. terrestrial, coastal, riparian/riverine, wetlands, marine, or other - describe
- Indicate the target category, e.g. vascular flora, non-vascular flora, vegetation community, birds, mammals, reptiles, frogs, invertebrates.
- Specify target species or community (if applicable)

- Indicate the types of data captured – for flora, indicate what was recorded, e.g. observations, species, count of individuals, marked individuals identification number, height, diameter at breast height, stem width, canopy width, condition and health information, reproductive status, age class, indicate if samples or specimens are collected, if photos are taken, and describe any other information collected relevant to the species of interest.
- Indicate the types of data captured – for fauna, indicate what was recorded, e.g. observations, species, count of individuals, marked individuals identification number, body weight, body measures, condition and health information, sex, reproductive status, age class, indicate if samples or specimens are collected, if photos are taken, if animals are fitted with any monitoring devices (i.e. a radio-collar), and describe any other information collected relevant to the species of interest.

2.3.1 Survey methods employed

Provide a summary of the methods employed. The EMSA Targeted Surveys Module can provide some guidance. Record:

- For all observations:
 - record how observations were made, e.g. details of general wanders/meanders (duration, route details, where the observers were looking), transects (length, width, layout), quadrats or plots (area and dimensions, and proximity to other plots)
- For flora observations:
 - record how observations were made, e.g. species presence recorded, individuals counted, individuals marked, diameter measured, canopy width measured, phenology recorded, specimen collected
- For fauna observations:
 - record how observations were made, e.g. if conducting a bird survey, list the number of surveyors, the equipment used, if call-playback was used (if so, what species, call type was played)
- For active searches:
 - record duration, number of observers, and typical activity (e.g. were observers lifting rocks – if so, all rocks, or a subset, and how was the subset determined, sifting through leaf litter, lifting bark, etc), and include what equipment was used
- For trapping:
 - record all details of the traps used (e.g. dimensions, trip mechanism and bait type for cages, and net size and mesh square size for mist nets), location, trap array information (including distances between traps), trap effort (e.g. how many nights were traps used for, were they open all day and night).

2.3.2 Observation equipment

For each item of key equipment used, record:

- Make, model and technical specifications – for items such as binoculars, spotting scopes, thermal scopes, camera traps, and acoustic recorders.
- For camera traps and acoustic recorders, also include all relevant setting information, as well as the specific location of the devices (location coordinates), heights and angles set at, micro-habitat information of the immediate area, the number of devices used, and the arrangement (including spacing between devices).

2.3.3 Personnel details, skills and experience

For each survey participant, record:

- Full name
- Associated organisation
- Experience surveying the target taxa, or similar taxa (a few sentences)
- Experience in identifying the target species (key information to justify that the surveyor is capable of accurately identifying the species, particularly if voucher specimens are not taken)
- Experience surveying the survey area (a few sentences)
- Role in the survey (key observer, data recorder)
- Relevant permits held (also recorded in the Permits and Authorities section).

2.3.4 Survey timing and survey conditions

Note the weather conditions encountered during the survey. For each key time interval (i.e. you may need to re-record every few hours), record:

- Temperature (e.g. closet BOM weather station or field weather station/gauge you may have)
- Cloud cover (e.g. clear, mostly clear, partly cloudy, cloudy, overcast)
- Rainfall (e.g. showers, rain, drizzle, frost, mist, thunderstorms)
- Rainfall duration (e.g. intermittent, occasional, frequent, continuous, periods of rain, brief)
- Wind direction (e.g. calm, light winds, moderate winds, fresh winds, strong winds, near gale, gale)
- Wind speed
- Weather conditions leading up to the survey. Whilst metrological records can be cross-checked at the time of the survey, a brief description of the conditions leading up to the survey can be a quick reference point. Note the conditions:
 - in the three months leading up to the survey. For example, note if conditions have been exceptionally dry, wet, or average.
 - in the seven days leading up to the survey. For example, if the week prior was cooler than usual weather, and the first day of the survey was the first warm sunny day.
- Moon phase (e.g. new moon, first quarter, full moon, third quarter)
- Tide position
- Site activities related to disturbance, development, construction and operations, such as ground disturbance, use of heavy machinery, vegetation clearance, dust, light and noise. Note activities:
 - in the three months leading up to the survey
 - in the seven days leading up to the survey.

When determining the survey effort to employ, review the species-specific guidelines for the species, similar species, or other species which similar methods are recommended. If environmental conditions are less than optimal, be flexible and allow for delaying survey effort until conditions improve. If the monitoring needs cannot be delayed, consider increasing survey effort, increasing the area to be surveyed, and look at alternative survey methods to increase the chance of detecting the species accurately. Consider the expected conditions, and the interactions of:

- Weather conditions (daytime, night time, and short- and long-term, i.e. consider the weather on the day, the night of, the previous week, and the seasonal conditions leading up to the survey – are conditions optimal? Or sub-optimal? Should the monitoring be delayed until optimal conditions are available?)
- Resource availability at the time of the survey, and leading up to the survey
- Moon phase and the impact of potentially increased light from a full moon, and the impact this may have on animal movements
- Fauna breeding times and population dynamics that influence animal movement and range
- Flora flowering and seeding times, and the impact that flowering and seeding has on increasing detectability
- Site disturbances – including recent, current and ongoing disturbances, such as stock grazing that may have significantly impacted flora species presence, or led to animal movement out of the area, as well as impacts from construction (road works, site developments, noise, vibration, etc.).
- Post-fire disturbances.

2.3.5 Survey visit and survey effort

For each visit, record:

- Visit start date
- Visit start time
- Visit end date
- Visit end time
- Comments about the timing of the visit should also be recorded. Such information could include 'unseasonal condition, warmer than usual day time temperatures experienced'. 'Overall habitat condition is conducive to climate data, indicating a later than usual summer'. Whilst anyone interrogating the data and examining the visit start and end dates with the available climate information could identify this themselves, it is useful to highlight this observation in the survey data itself.

For standardisation, each survey occurrence is called a visit – a single instance the survey methodology was conducted. A visit can take place over multiple days. A systematic search along a series of transects constituting an identified project area is a single visit. A 4-7 day trapping event at the location is a single visit.

For each survey visit (i.e. a survey interval that forms part of the monitoring, as a minimum daily), record:

- Start date
- Start time
- End date
- End time
- Total duration (ideally to hours, or minutes for shorter surveys)
- Number of surveyors (distinguishing active survey participants and data entry only participants if relevant)
- Visit type – note if the visit is for a reconnaissance survey to scope out the survey area, an initial visit to commence basic survey techniques, the core part of the monitoring, or a

follow-up revisit to check anything missed/additional observations at a different time of day etc.

- Timing appropriateness – record information to justify the timing of the survey. For example, is it the correct time of year, season, seasonal conditions, time of day and weather conditions to be able to observe the species of interest?
- Survey frequency – indicate the frequency of the surveys, e.g. weekly, monthly, bi-annual.

2.4 Survey site information

2.4.1 Location and mapped data information

All observations of threatened species, and the location of monitoring survey sites, must be recorded as accurately as possible, ideally with a GNSS or DGPS device. Records must identify the location (ideally in latitude and longitude), datum, accuracy, precision, along with the site identifier and data of the observation.

The Australian Government *Guidelines for biological survey and mapped data* (Commonwealth of Australia 2018) sets information for how monitoring data, surveys, maps and other spatial and metadata should be prepared. Whilst not mandatory, these guidelines are recommended.

Where possible, and where permit and land access permissions enable, dedicated monitoring survey sites should be permanently marked, ideally with star droppers (TERN recommend 1.4 m high star droppers).

2.4.2 Site description

Depending on the species of interest and habitat, record information to describe the survey site. The EMSA Plot Description Module can provide some guidance. Record:

- Landform pattern and landform element
- Soils and geology
- Slope and aspect
- Lithology of any outcrops
- Lithology of any surface fragments and size
- Lithology and any further details of key habitat refuge elements important to the target species (including the abundance/frequency of suitable refuges, and absence of suitable refuges)
- Site disturbances – including erosion type, weeds, fire, clearance, rubbish
- Land use history – where possible, use existing standards such as the Australian Land Use Management (ALUM) classification (information is included in the EMSA Plot Description Module)
- Fire history and any fire-related information that may be important to the target species.

2.4.3 Photopoints

Take photos of your survey site for visual reference. The EMSA Photopoints Module provides some guidance.

- Take a series of photos that best represent the overall habitat, vegetation, and landform of the survey area. Landscape photos (not portrait) are best.

- Consider taking a series of 360° panoramas from 3 points in the centre of the survey location, following the guidance in the EMSA Photopoints Module.

2.5 Observations

2.5.1 Observation methods

Depending on your target species and taxon type, record how observations were made. Record:

- Broad observation methods, for example, seen, heard, signs, captured
- Detailed observation methods: for example, seen whilst spotlighting, seen via remote camera, seen via helicopter, signs – scats, tracks, hair, wallows, captured – hand capture, pitfall trap, cage trap, Malaise trap, sweep net, etc.). A full list is available in the EMSA Opportune Module.

2.5.2 Direct observations

For each observation made, note what information will be collected. Record:

- Presence/absence or non-detection, count – estimate, count – actual, abundance or frequency, cover estimates, or cover – actual (describe how cover was calculated)
- Identify if absences will be recorded
- Measurements of individuals (i.e. morphology and taxonomic measurements recorded)
- Age-class of fauna individuals (i.e. if individuals observed are assigned an age class, e.g. adult, immature, juvenile, larvae, etc)
- Clinical samples of individuals (i.e. if swabs are taken).

2.5.3 Indirect observations

For signs of presence, include the context of the sign – i.e. record where a scat was encountered, i.e. for Koala scats found under a tree, record the species of tree (and additional information if specifically targeting koalas, i.e. health status of the tree, height, and proximity to other trees, signs of scratchings).

Recording information on the substrate, leaf litter coverage, and the depth, to provide context on the likelihood of signs being observed. I.e. tracks are unlikely to be observed in areas of high leaf litter coverage.

For scats, take note of the colour and moisture to help estimate age since deposited. Take photos, and where possible, gain additional evidence to support the species determined, i.e. tracks in the sand leading up to the scat.

Predator scats, including feral cats, foxes, dingos, and pellets from owls should be collected to enable prey item species identifications from bone and hairs present.

2.6 Species verifications

Include information on how you established species verifications. This may apply to the species of interest, the habitat/vegetation association information, or any other plant/animal species monitoring as part of the project. Record:

- If species were identified by the surveyor using their experience, reference guides

- If vouchers were taken, and if so, where are they to be deposited—herbaria/museum, etc. Also, note voucher numbers and voucher type (herbarium voucher, leaf tissue voucher, whole animal, animal tissue).

It is important to utilise existing species name standards, such as:

- Australian Fauna Directory (AFD)
- Australian Plant Name Index 9 APNI)
- Australian Plant Census (APC).

Record the certainty of the species determination, and note if the observation is confirmed (accurate determination, and/or voucher available, and/or photographs available), or doubtful (unconfirmed).

2.7 Habitat information

2.7.1 Vegetation community

Ensure the major vegetation group, or even better, the vegetation association, has been effectively described – this is applicable to all ecological surveys. The EMSA Vegetation Mapping Module provides some guidance. Record:

- Major vegetation group (examples include Rainforest and Vine Thickets, Eucalypt Tall Open Forests, Eucalypt Woodlands, Acacia Open Woodlands, Mallee Woodlands and Shrublands, Heathlands and Chenopod Shrublands). A full list is available in the EMSA Opportune Module.
- Vegetation association (to the best NVIS level description you can manage/feel appropriate)
- Dominant overstorey species, growth form, and average height, estimated foliage projective cover
- Dominant mid-storey species, growth form, and average height, estimated foliage projective cover
- Dominant understorey species, growth form, and average height, estimated foliage projective cover
- Height of the tallest stratum
- Weed/invasives abundance.

2.7.2 Floristic composition

Depending on the species of interest, detailed information on the floristics of the survey area may be beneficial. Collating a species inventory of the survey area is important if understanding the vegetation community is important to the target species of interest, but also for assessing if key species that indicate the species presence/absence become important.

Record:

- List all flora species present within the survey area, and ideally, for each species, record the growth form (tree, shrub, forb etc.) and key phenology stage present, particularly if flowering and seeding. The EMSA Floristics Module provides some guidance.

2.7.3 Habitat elements

For habitat resources identified, record the location and description, including the area size, and take representative photos. Depending on the species of interest, it may be appropriate to also record the aspect (i.e. for shelter sites, including cave entrances, rock crevices and rock overhang sites).

For target trees, including food trees and hollow-bearing trees, record the tree species (actual species if known, if not a voucher name/number). When specifically searching for potential hollow-bearing trees, also record the location and/or count in a defined area of non-hollow-bearing trees. For hollows identified, recording the height of the hollow entrance, the aspect of the hollow entrance, the size (visual estimate) of the entrance, and the estimated average diameter of the branch/trunk. When surveying for food or perch trees, record the health of the tree (see x codes).

2.8 Data availability and access

All monitoring data of threatened species is considered valuable. This extends to monitoring of areas where threatened species are thought to be located, but were not detected during surveys. Non-detection records are still crucial to understanding a species' distribution, abundance, conservation status, and linking to past and current threatening processes.

All threatened species monitoring datasets should be shared so they have the opportunity to contribute to a better understanding of the species. To ensure awareness of the dataset and potentially enable access and re-use of the data, ensure the following information is recorded:

- How data was collected (i.e. specialised web-app/app, hard copy data sheet, field notebook)
- Where data will be stored (i.e. which database will the data be provided to)
- Dataset title, and identify if there are any additional linked datasets of relevance.
- Where data will be stored (i.e. which database will the data be provided to)
- Data custodian and contact details
- Important restrictions of the data, including privacy sensitivities and applicable embargoes.

Camera traps, and acoustic and ultrasonic recording devices are recommended ways to collect valuable ecological information, and are referenced in many of the species-specific protocols. However, analysing the images and recordings can be very time intensive and expensive. An Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) project is working to make the processing and analysis of camera trap and acoustic data more accessible through the 'WildObs' and 'Open Ecoacoustics' initiatives. These programs aim to develop systems to transform how Australia handles wildlife camera and acoustic data by creating national platforms powered by AI. You can contact WildObs via the [Wildobs website](#) and Open Ecoacoustics via the [Open Ecoacoustics website](#) for more information.

If using the Ecological Monitoring System of Australia (EMSA), the [Targeted Surveys Module](#) enables metadata information on surveys to be recorded in a standardised format. The module does not collect or record field data. If EMSA has not been used, liaise with State/Commonwealth jurisdictions for advice on the most appropriate data repository. Ideally, all data will be contributed to the Australian Government's Biodiversity Data Repository.

Sharing of information from private land and co-managed land does need to be carefully considered. In 2024 DCCEEW held discussions about how data is shared and managed in the Biodiversity Data Repository. A small working group of interested NRM delivery partners was formed. Outcomes of the working group were summarised, and used to inform DCCEEWs guidelines and policies. Information is available on the [Environmental Information Policy and Guidance website](#).

3 Species-specific guidelines

3.1 Birds

3.1.1 Australasian Bittern, *Botaurus poiciloptilus*

The literature review of the monitoring methods relating to the Australasian Bittern (*Botaurus poiciloptilus*) identified some key points that must be addressed when developing species-specific survey guidelines (TERN 2024d). These points are listed below.

- The need for a standardised national monitoring approach to assess population trends of Australasian Bittern is well recognised (DBCA 2018, Threatened Species Scientific Committee (TSSC) 2019, Garnett and Baker 2021, Commonwealth of Australia 2022, BirdLife International 2023). A national monitoring program should incorporate known sites across the range, and strategically target potential habitats on private property (Garnett and Baker 2021, BirdLife International 2023).
- Monitoring typically includes a combination of survey methods, with the core method being call-based surveys, to confirm the presence of the species and provide counts of breeding males. This can be done via autonomous recording devices (i.e. Song Meters), which can be left in the field, or in-person passive acoustic surveys. Camera traps and thermal drones are fast becoming standard components of monitoring. Other approaches include in-person direct counts and satellite and radio tracking.
- Surveys generally take place between September to December (breeding season), before sunrise or after sunset. Analysis of survey data has shown that the best time to detect Australasian Bitterns is 1 hour before sunrise, in September, on a moonlit night with no clouds or rain.
- Several targeted Australasian Bittern monitoring projects are being undertaken using a combination of technologies, with a range of recent survey reports and data available. BirdLife Australia runs a dedicated Bittern Recovery project which commenced in the 2008-2009 breeding season and oversees volunteer-based surveys, with data entered directly into the BirdData App.
- The need for a standardised approach to monitoring is well recognised (TSSC 2011, DBCA 2018, Commonwealth of Australia 2019). The New Zealand Department of Conservation (O'Donnell and Williams 2015) has developed protocols for monitoring Australasian Bittern in New Zealand, including detailed field and data analysis instructions, which can form the basis of a standardised monitoring protocol for Australia.
- Improved knowledge of the species' biology and ecology, particularly of movement patterns, breeding and habitat use, will assist in developing and implementing a standardised monitoring strategy.

The EMSA modules that can be leveraged for this species include the [Vertebrate Fauna Module](#) (bird surveys, and acoustic and ultrasonic surveys protocols) (O'Neill et al. 2023), and the Opportune Module (Bignall et al. 2023a).

3.1.2 Eastern Curlew, *Numenius madagascariensis*

The literature review of the monitoring methods relating to the Eastern Curlew (*Numenius madagascariensis*) has identified some key points that must be considered when developing species-specific survey guidelines (TERN 2024f). These points are listed below.

- Hightide counts of roosting birds are favoured over low tide counts of foraging birds as the birds are easier to count when they are congregated and inactive in their roosting spots.
 - Surveys should be conducted during the four-hour period around high tide.
- Demarcating and mapping shorebird areas that contain closed groups of birds (i.e. birds that remain exclusively within the area during the non-breeding period) is important for accurate and repeatable counts.
- A single shorebird survey area should be divided into discrete counting areas (e.g. known roosting locations).
- At large shorebird areas where there are many counting areas, the chance of double counting birds is greater and therefore, simultaneous counting strategies should be considered.
- The most logical way to perform simultaneous counts is to allocate counting areas to multiple groups of surveyors and have all the groups survey their counting areas concurrently.
- To limit count variability, sites should ideally be surveyed more than once during the peak of the non-breeding period.
- If only one count is possible, then this should be conducted in January. If more are possible, they should be conducted in November and/or December.
- A winter survey between mid-May and mid-August can be used to estimate juvenile numbers.
- Aerial surveys are generally not suitable as this species is highly sensitive to invasive survey techniques.
 - Aerial surveys may, however, be useful as reconnaissance surveys to identify foraging and roosting areas and access points for ground counts.
 - Banding and satellite tracking can provide information on Eastern Curlew's migration routes and local movements in their non-breeding areas in Australia.

The [Fauna Ground Counts Module](#) (McCallum et al. 2023b) can be leveraged for this species.

3.1.3 Hooded Plover (eastern), *Thinornis cucullatus cucullatus*

The literature review of the monitoring methods relating to the Eastern Hooded Plover (*Thinornis cucullatus cucullatus*) identified some key points that must be addressed when developing species-specific survey guidelines (TERN 2024g). These points are listed below.

- BirdLife Australia has been managing a robust monitoring program, biennially surveying the entire Eastern Hooded Plover population since 1980. Updates to the protocol occurred in 2010, improving survey data collection methods by creating fixed survey routes, typically with sensible start and end points that correspond with site access and bird territories.
- The BirdLife count surveys that are undertaken every two years are suitable for population monitoring of Hooded Plover's, as these birds are relatively long-lived and it takes time for breeding success to translate into changes at the population level (Weston 2003). Additionally, the size of this monitoring program is extensive so coordinating surveys more frequently with the resources available may be unsustainable.
- BirdLife Australia has also run a successful project protecting and monitoring the nesting success of Hooded Plovers across their population. Since the inception of this program, nesting success has, in some areas, increased from 0-5% to ~50 % (Mead and Maguire 2020). Survey visits to a breeding pair occur at least weekly for around three months to monitor success from nesting to fledging.
- Monitoring is recommended during the breeding season (August to May) when birds are territorial and at their most sedentary and, therefore, least likely to be double-counted. The biennial count occurs in mid-November in even years (i.e. 2020, 2022 etc.) (BirdLife Australia 2022). When birds are most active, it is recommended to survey in the early morning or late evening (before the sun goes down), and short flushing from their nests is less likely to result in nest temperature fluctuation. Avoid surveying in the hour before or after high tide as the transect followed is likely to cross nesting territory and present a risk to vulnerable nests or chicks (Maguire 2017).
- BirdLife Australia utilises volunteers to undertake most of its surveys. Volunteers are provided with training in the form of workshops, resources and mentorship to ensure monitoring protocols are followed before undertaking surveys, and additional training is required before undertaking nest success monitoring.
- BirdLife Australia uses the online portal BirdData, in which data can be entered directly in the field (Daws and Tan 2017). Traditional hardcopy data sheets are also available for those not confident using the technology in the field, and data is entered post-survey by the surveyor or BirdLife Australia staff.
- Several groups undertake banding and flagging of Hooded Plovers to monitor and study their survival and movements. Appropriate size and design of bands and flags are available from the Australian Bird and Bat Banding Scheme (ABBBS). Size 5 bands and flags with a 5 mm inner diameter are recommended for Hooded Plovers.
- The most common method for capture is using a leg noose carpet to tangle the bird's feet before capturing by hand or hand net (Weston et al. 2004, Weston et al. 2020). However, birds have also been shown to become transfixed by a spotlight in nocturnal surveys, allowing for close approach and capture by hand (Dennis and Ball 2013).
- Standard morphological measurements include: weight, length of head plus bill, culmen, wing and tarsus (Dennis and Ball 2013, Lees et al. 2019). Sex may be determined by genetic analysis, and therefore, blood samples of 50-90 µl may be taken during capture.

The [Fauna Ground Counts Module](#) (McCallum et al. 2023b) can be leveraged for this species.

3.1.4 King Island Scrubtit, *Acanthornis magna greeniana*

The literature review of the monitoring methods relating to the King Island Scrubtit (*Acanthornis magna greeniana*) has identified some key points to be considered when developing species-specific survey guidelines (TERN 2024). These points are listed below.

- A robust survey methodology for collecting presence/absence data and abundance estimates using call playback is in use for the King Island Scrubtit, and its procedure has been justified and refined in several publications (Donaghey 2011, Webb et al. 2016, Webb and Crates 2019, Bell and Webb 2023).
- Surveys are usually undertaken in the birds' non-breeding season when they are generally more difficult to detect as they are less territorial during this period. This is because their habitat is difficult for surveyors to navigate during the wetter months when the sub-species is likely to be breeding.
- Current survey methodology suggests that five-minute surveys using call playback are repeated three times during a survey period to ensure presence/absence data is accurate (Webb et al. 2016).
- Inaccuracy and gaps in the understanding of the distribution of vegetation communities have been identified as significant barriers to the conservation of the King Island Scrubtit (Webb et al. 2016, Bell and Webb 2023). Ongoing surveys accurately classifying vegetation communities across King Island may be used to project area stratification and create vegetation maps useful for survey planning.
- The EMSA Vegetation Mapping Module outlines the steps for classifying the vegetation community (Bignall et al. 2023c) and includes the collection of additional co-variants outlined in the vegetation surveys completed alongside King Island Scrubtit surveys (Donaghey 2011, Bell and Webb 2023).
- The presence of coarse woody debris (CWD) strongly predicted King Island Scrubtit presence (Bell and Webb 2023). Survey planning and habitat mapping for the King Island Scrubtit should, therefore, include coarse woody debris as a factor. The EMSA Coarse Woody Debris Module (McCallum et al. 2023a) provides procedures and guidelines for recording coarse woody debris abundance, dimensions, and level of decay to estimate the length and volume of CWD present in wooded systems.
- Current research suggests that the area of occupancy and extent of occurrence may require re-evaluation as an outcome of recent monitoring and updates to vegetation maps for King Island (Bell and Webb 2023). This is likely to have implications for the locations of future monitoring of the King Island Scrubtit.

The [EMSA Vertebrate Fauna Module](#) (Bird surveys, and Acoustic and ultrasonic surveys protocols) (O'Neill et al. 2023) can be leveraged for this species.

3.1.6 Noisy Scrub-bird, Tjamiluk, *Atrichornis clamosus*

The literature review of the monitoring methods relating to the Noisy Scrub-bird (*Atrichornis clamosus*) has identified some key points that must be addressed when developing species-specific survey guidelines (TERN 2024p). These points are listed below.

- Noisy Scrub-bird are highly cryptic and most commonly monitored by census of calling males during periods in their breeding season. The relationship between calling male numbers and the true population is not known (Burbidge et al. 2018), therefore, monitoring only provides an index of the true population (Smith 1985, Danks et al. 1996, Comer et al. 2010, Roberts et al. 2020)
- Standardising the methods in which monitoring occurs will add reliability to inferences drawn from trends in the population index.
- Surveys are typically undertaken during the Noisy Scrub-bird's breeding season (April – October) (Portelli 2004, Roberts et al. 2020) in the three hours after sunrise or three hours before sunset (Smith and Forrester 1981) when the birds are likely to be most active.
- Providing standards for transect length/ distance between sample sites, duration of surveys, how call playback may be utilised as well as standardising the weather, climate, location and vegetation observations recorded will benefit the reliability of the data collected. Allow for repeat surveys and robustness of inferences made from the data collected.
- Monitoring using permanent or semi-permanent acoustic monitoring devices has not been well documented for the Noisy Scrub-bird, however, it is mentioned, without detail in at least one document (Comer et al. 2018). It is therefore likely that monitoring is currently occurring, but the documentation is not publicly available. Monitoring using permanent acoustic monitoring devices is cost-effective and practical, enabling large amounts of data to be recorded; however this also means a lot of post-recording processing and unlike in-person surveys, the direction of calls cannot be determined (Pickering 2018).
- Live capture is not recommended as a standard approach to monitoring the Noisy Scrub-bird population, as they are difficult to capture and the process takes a lot of time and effort (Danks 1994, 1997, Portelli 2004). Males and females also require different modes of capture (Danks 1997, Berryman 2007, Comer et al. 2010, Kemp et al. 2015, Morris et al. 2015). Capture has however, been utilised for translocation and radiotracking studies, but not standard population monitoring.

The EMSA [Vegetation Mapping Module](#) (Bignall et al. 2023c) may be relevant to surveying the Noisy Scrub-bird.

3.1.7 Plains-wanderer, *Pedionomus torquatus*

The literature review of the monitoring methods relating to the Plains-wanderer (*Pedionomus torquatus*) has identified the following key points that must be considered when developing species-specific survey guidelines. (TERN 2024s). These points are listed below.

- Traditionally, the most effective method to detect the Plains-wanderer was spotlight transect surveys over suitable grassland habitat, at night from a very slow-moving (<5 km/h) vehicle with a handheld spotlight and vehicle headlights (DEWHA 2010).
- Infrared thermography transect surveys conducted in the same manner as spotlight transect surveys are emerging as a valuable detection method. However, differences in detection rates between spotlight and infrared thermography survey techniques are still being investigated along with an infrared thermography monitoring protocol (Nugent 2019).
- Based on the strong similarities between the survey techniques, it is recommended that spotlight and infrared thermography transect surveys be covered under the same guidelines.
- High-resolution thermal cameras ($\geq 320 \times 240$) have been found to provide improved detection capabilities compared to traditional spotlights, and have been recommended to be implemented as best practice for nocturnal surveys of small endotherms (Dawlings et al. 2023).
- Handheld video camera-style thermal cameras have been found to be more comfortable to hold and view than thermal scopes where users look directly through the lens (Dawlings et al. 2023).
- The encounter rate of individuals detected per kilometre of spotlight/infrared thermography transect traversed provides a reliable abundance index.
- The speed that the vehicle travels, distance between parallel transects, length of each transect, total length of the transects, location of the transects, start and end time of the survey, weather conditions, number, name and experience of observers, number and strength of spotlights (and/or number of infrared thermal cameras) used, and distance either side of the vehicle that is being surveyed are important metadata that should be collected during a transect survey.
- It is important that spotlight and infrared thermography transect surveys are undertaken on nights where there is no wind or only a light breeze, and either no rain or light showers (DEWHA 2010a).
- To monitor population demographic parameters such as abundance and breeding status, detected individuals that can held in a spotlight beam are able to be approached by a second observer on foot and captured by hand or using a hand-held fisherman's landing net (Harrington et al. 1988).
- Acoustic monitoring using song meters can be used to detect the species based on species-specific vocalisations since female Plains-wanderers produce a unique call (Baker-Gabb 2018, Rowe et al. 2024).
- Song meters can be used to determine the occurrence of Plains-wanderers at the landscape scale, including detecting new and transient populations. The results of acoustic monitoring can inform the location of follow-up spotlight or infrared thermography transect surveys (Rowe et al. 2024).
- The maximum distance of 180 m at which a song meter can detect a Plains-wanderer call under ideal conditions should be considered when deploying song meters (Rowe and Balasubramaniam 2020).

- Song meters should be programmed to only record during the early morning and evening when Plains-wanderers call to limit the size and processing requirement of recordings (Frith 1969, Rowe et al. 2024).
- The make and model of the song meter, deployment location, deployment and retrieval date, programmed recording schedule/s, sampling rate, audio signal type, and name and experience of observers are important metadata that should be collected during acoustic monitoring.
- Reliable and accessible Plains-wanderer call recognisers are required for automated detection of the species from song meter recordings. Rowe et al. (2024) used the software program Kaleidoscope Pro (v. 5.1.9, Wildlife Acoustics, Maynard, MA, USA) to provide a Plains-wanderer recogniser that could be implemented by a range of end users, including volunteers and land managers, without requiring advanced training to run the recogniser and validate the output. Kaleidoscope has a user-friendly interface, high acoustic data processing speed, and ongoing customer support capabilities. The software creates a vocalisation template using a Hidden Markov Model clustering algorithm, which has been shown to be effective at balancing correct identifications of target species while minimising detections of false positives (Trifa et al. 2008, Chu and Blumstein 2011).
- Monitoring the structure of grassland habitat is recommended to determine if it is suitable for the presence of the species (Baker-Gabb et al. 2016, Schultz et al. 2017), and can be used to microsite the location of spotlight or infrared thermography transect surveys.
- The 'golf ball method' is a simple method for the rapid assessment of grassland structure using golf balls (Schultz 2007; Schultz and Morgan 2010), which has been widely used to discern suitable grassland habitat for the Plains-wanderer (Baker-Gabb et al. 2016).
- It is recommended that complementary grassland structure data be recorded from within the 1 m² quadrat frame used in the golf ball method, including:
 - Cover and height of native and introduced grasses.
 - Cover and height of native and introduced herbs.
 - Cover of litter, bare ground and cryptogamic crust.
- The golf ball method is not suitable for discerning suitable marginal Plains-wanderer habitat, including low crops of cereal grasses and cereal stubble, and sparse chenopod shrublands. Therefore, an investigation into monitoring marginal habitat to determine if it is suitable for the presence of the species is recommended.
- Visually assessing grassland structure to determine areas that are suitable for the Plains-wanderer can be conducted using a photographic guide with reference photographs of grasslands (Parker and Oliver 2006), and is required prior to undertaking nocturnal transect surveys to microsite survey locations (DEWHA 2010a).
- Investigation into visually assessing marginal Plains-wanderer habitat, including low crops of cereal grasses and cereal stubble, and sparse chenopod shrublands, to determine if it is suitable for the presence of the species is recommended.

The EMSA modules that can be leveraged for this species include the [Vertebrate Fauna Module](#) (Bird surveys, and Acoustic and ultrasonic surveys protocols) (O'Neill et al. 2023), and [Fauna Ground Counts Module](#) (McCallum et al. 2023b)

3.2 Frogs

3.2.1 Southern Bell Frog, *Litoria raniformis*

The literature review of the monitoring methods relating to the Southern Bell Frog, or Growling Grass Frog, (*Litoria raniformis*) has identified some key points that must be addressed when developing species-specific survey guidelines (TERN 2024t). These points are listed below.

- Using more than one method, on repeated occasions, to detect the Southern Bell Frog is recommended, not least of all as male *L. raniformis* can exhibit variable calling behaviour (Heard et al. 2006).
- Visual counts are likely to underestimate population size for Southern Bell Frogs, so mark-recapture is recommended to more accurately estimate the size of the population (Koehler et al. 2015).
- To determine occupancy during a single season, it is advised that all required surveys are begun and completed within the block of months in which the requirement for the desired cumulative probability of detection does not change (Heard et al. 2010). For example, when pursuing a threshold cumulative probability of detection 0.95, these blocks are October-December (two surveys required), and January-March (three surveys required).
- Heard, Scroggie and Clemann (2010) recommend that larval sampling surveys occur in December and January, as these are the only months in which a cumulative probability of detection of 0.95 or 0.99 can be attained, using the techniques outlined in Heard et al. (2006).
- Acoustic monitoring can be an ideal detection technique for frog species as it does not disturb the target species during data collection, and eliminates any requirement to find visually cryptic species (Measey et al. 2017), such the Southern Bell Frog. Casey (2020) has successfully undertaken automated bioacoustic monitoring programs to record and describe the call behaviour of this species.

The EMSA [Vertebrate Fauna Module](#) (Acoustic and ultrasonic surveys protocols) (O'Neill et al. 2023) can be leveraged for this species.

3.2.2 Mountain Frog, *Philoria kundagungan*

The literature review of the monitoring methods relating to the Mountain Frog (*Philoria kundagungan*) has identified some key points that must be addressed when developing species-specific survey guidelines (TERN 2024n). These points are listed below.

- The Mountain Frog is a cryptic species and difficult to detect when conducting passive on-ground surveys. Simulation of male advertisement calling using call playback to elicit a response has been used successfully in occupancy studies (Bolitho et al. 2021, Heard et al. 2023).
- Monitoring using an occupancy framework model is effective for estimating occupancy rates in species that have a detection probability of less than one (MacKenzie et al. 2002). These surveys require multiple site visits during a single survey period and the collection of covariate information to feed into the occupancy model.
- A recent study by (Bolitho et al. 2023) using bioacoustics developed a robust audio recognition algorithm that allows the Mountain Frog to be monitored continuously throughout the year. The study provides a baseline for future monitoring for the detection of change in response to disturbances such as climate change and fire.
- Species of the genus *Philoria* are difficult to differentiate between as their colour, pattern and body shape overlap, and the male's advertisement calls are indistinguishable. The species are however, allopatric and aside from genotyping the geographical range is the most reliable way to differentiate one species from another (Knowles et al. 2004).
- The Mountain Frog has been most frequently detected above 850 m in altitude (Bolitho et al. 2021) and the area of potential habitat suitable for the Mountain Frog is estimated to be 11 km² (Bolitho et al. 2021).
- Like other montane amphibian species, calling is driven by temperature change and precipitation cues (Willacy et al. 2015, Bolitho et al. 2023). They are most likely to call when the substrate temperature is greater than 11 °C and call most frequently at 13.8 °C. This makes them vulnerable to, and indicators of, anthropogenically driven climate change (Laurance et al. 2011, Bolitho et al. 2021).

The EMSA modules that can be leveraged for this species include the [Vertebrate Fauna Module](#) (Acoustic and ultrasonic surveys protocols) (O'Neill et al. 2023), and the [Vegetation Mapping Module](#) (Bignall et al. 2023c) may also be relevant.

3.2.3 Mountain-top Nursery-frog, *Cophixalus monticola*

The literature review of the monitoring methods relating to the Mountain-top Nursery-frog (*Cophixalus monticola*) has identified some key points that must be considered when developing species-specific survey guidelines (TERN 2024m). These points are listed below.

- The species is known from a single, isolated locality on Mt Lewis on the Carbine Tableland, northwest of Cairns in Far North Queensland.
- Its estimated extent of occurrence is estimated to be 34 km², with an estimated area of occupancy of 20 km² (IUCN SSC Amphibian Specialist Group 2022). Monitoring should focus in the estimated extent of occurrence.
- The species is difficult to detect visually. Advertisement call vocalisations from males during the wet season are therefore the key indicator of presence (Richards et al. 1994, Hoskin 2004, Shoo and Williams 2004). Males almost always call from elevated sites and produce a short trill (Hoskin 2004).
- Calls should be analysed for characteristics including dominant frequency (the frequency at which the call is of greatest intensity), duration (beginning of the first pulse to the end of the last pulse), number of notes, number of pulses, and note or pulse rate (number of notes or pulses divided by call duration).
- Call surveys should be undertaken on wet, humid nights (>80% relative humidity), conditions expected to be conducive to calling activity by the species (Shoo and Williams 2004).
- The majority of the breeding observations for Australian microhylid frogs, including the Mountain-top Nursery-frog, have been recorded in the lead-up to and during the wet season between October and February (Hoskin 2004).
- Temperature should be recorded along with calls, as it can strongly influence the pulse rate and call repetition rate of calls for most species (DEWHA 2010b).
- Standardised surveys consisting of a slow-paced walk for 10 minutes along a 50 m transect, with calls identified to individuals 10 m either side of the transect, have been used to calculate a relative abundance index for the species (i.e. number of calling males per transect; Shoo and Williams 2004).
- Strip transect width should be determined by locating at least six calling males of the target species in similar habitat and calculating the mean maximum distance at which calls can be heard and identified (DEWHA 2010b).
- Call playback may be used to stimulate present but non-calling males to call in response to initiate a static call survey. However, the effectiveness of call playback for this species remains undocumented.
- Monitoring habitat condition is also important for the conservation of this species, which requires the presence of *Linospadix* palms with gathered decaying leaf litter for breeding and high levels of soil and leaf-litter moisture to prevent desiccation of the eggs during development (Williams 2007).

The EMSA modules that can be leveraged for this species include the Vertebrate Fauna Module (Acoustic and ultrasonic surveys protocols) (O'Neill et al. 2023), and the Vegetation Mapping Module (Bignall et al. 2023c) may also be relevant.

3.3 Mammals

3.3.1 Brush-tailed Rock-wallaby, *Petrogale penicillata*

The literature review of the monitoring methods relating to the Brush-tailed Rock-wallaby (*Petrogale penicillata*) identified some key points that must be addressed when developing species-specific survey guidelines (TERN 2024e). These points are listed below.

- Accessing colonies to survey the remnant populations can be difficult, however, the recent research by Shannon Kleeman and colleagues on the population in Victoria's Grampians National Park highlights a modern, comprehensive and minimally invasive approach to this monitoring (Kleemann et al. 2022).
- As the primary habitat of this species is rugged escarpments, where possible scat collection is made at, or below, these inhabited escarpments (Short 1989, Tuft et al. 2011, Phillips et al. 2022).
- DNA can be obtained from fresh scats to identify individual wallabies, determine pedigrees, recruitment, dispersal and movements (Bluff et al. 2011, Piggott et al. 2018, Kleemann et al. 2022).
- Camera surveys for the Brush-tailed Rock-wallaby can provide non-invasive monitoring of an area to try and detect the species (Lavery et al. 2021), or can be used to directly monitor a population.
- Brush-tailed rock-wallabies can be directly captured, tagged and counted using treadle-release soft-walled cage traps (Bluff et al. 2011). Capture-mark-recapture methodologies can then be used to assess key demographic parameters.
- Home ranges of Brush-tailed Rock-wallabies can be assessed using VHF or GPS telemetry, as done for the reintroduced population in the Grampians National Park, Victoria (Molyneux et al. 2011).

The EMSA modules that can be leveraged for this species include the [Vertebrate Fauna Module](#) (Trapping protocols) (O'Neill et al. 2023), [Camera Trapping Module](#) (Laws et al. 2024) [Signs-based Fauna Surveys](#) (Cox et al. 2023) and [Fauna Ground Counts Module](#) (McCallum et al. 2023b).

3.3.2 Western Quoll, Chuditch, *Dasyurus geoffroii*

The literature review of the monitoring methods relating to the Western Quoll (*Dasyurus geoffroii*) has identified some key points that must be addressed when developing species-specific survey guidelines (TERN 2024x). These points are listed below.

- Cage trapping, camera traps, radio-tracking and scat analysis are well-established monitoring methods that are highly efficient and applicable to monitoring the Western Quoll.
- There is room for standardisation of methods, such as spacing of cage and camera traps, noting that this is primarily driven by quoll home ranges, which can vary depending on habitat, fox/cat control, sex, age-class and breeding. Hence, a 200 m spacing for cage traps may be appropriate for the abundant reintroduced Ikara-Flinders Ranges National Park population and for smaller female home ranges, but it would likely be too much for a more arid/resource-poor location.
- Standardising trap bait to chicken wings may offer some advantages for intra- and inter-site comparisons, especially where trap bycatch such as Woylies is a major confounding issue. However, a preliminary review of trapping results from the Ikara-Flinders Ranges National Park has found the universal bait and rabbit bait had comparable results (K. Moseby pers. comm.), hence, where bycatch is not a major confounding issue, bait type may not greatly impact quoll trapping results.
- The length of time cage trapping and camera traps are set in an area could be standardised. Cage trapping for five nights appears to be accepted in WA and SA. However, both regions report new animals still being caught after five nights of trapping. Five nights, therefore, is a compromise between the guidelines of capture-mark-recapture population assessment and cost.
- For camera traps, 2-4 weeks is often the minimum recommended, and 30 days should be considered where possible to provide strong confidence in presence/absence (Meek *et al.* 2014).
- Radio-tracking is an established monitoring method to help assess specific Western Quoll demographics, home range and den site attributes, and the timing and causes of mortality. It is much more sensitive than cage trapping and camera traps and can be critical to identifying causes of quoll mortality and achieving reintroduction success (Moseby *et al.* 2015, Moseby *et al.* 2021). An area for possible standardisation is the percentage of a translocated Western Quoll population that should be monitored by radio-collaring to assess best survival, home ranges, dispersal and causes of mortality, noting though, that this is predominantly driven by cost and available funds, and the human resources available to monitor the collared quolls effectively.

The EMSA modules that can be leveraged for this species include the [Vertebrate Fauna Module](#) (Trapping protocols) (O'Neill *et al.* 2023), [Camera Trapping Module](#) (Laws *et al.* 2024) [Signs-based Fauna Surveys](#) (Cox *et al.* 2023) and [Fauna Ground Counts Module](#) (McCallum *et al.* 2023b).

3.3.3 Eastern Quoll, Luaner, *Dasyurus viverrinus*

The literature review of the monitoring methods relating to the Eastern Quoll (*Dasyurus viverrinus*) has identified some key points that must be addressed when developing species-specific survey guidelines (TERN 2024h). These points are listed below.

- Cage trapping, camera trapping and radio-tracking are well established survey methods that are highly functional and applicable to the monitoring of the Eastern Quoll. There is room for standardisation of methods, such as spacing of cage and camera traps, noting though that this is primarily driven by quoll home ranges, which can vary depending on habitat.
- Standardising bait to chicken wings, the standard bait for Western Quoll trapping in south-west WA, may offer some advantages for intra- and inter-site comparisons, especially where trap bycatch is a major confounding issue. However, where bycatch is not a major confounding issue, bait type may not greatly impact Eastern Quoll trapping results.
- The duration of cage trapping and camera trapping surveys be standardised. For cage trapping, Godsell (1983) initially trapped for three nights but changed to two nights to mitigate weight loss in repeatedly trapped quolls. Fancourt et al. (2013) utilised the more thermally protective standard PVC devil pipe traps and trapped for the more standard five nights. As this trap is now the standard trapping device (required where devils are sympatric), five nights represents a compromise between the precepts of capture-mark-recapture population assessment and cost.
- For camera traps, 2-4 weeks is recommended, although there is no detection asymptote established for the Eastern Quoll (Meek et al. 2014), 30 days should probably be the standardised minimum to provide strong confidence in presence/absence and relative abundance. This doesn't preclude a quoll being present in the vicinity of that camera outside that monitoring period, perhaps on mainland Australia in the vicinity of a reported sighting, as per Hope et al. (2022).
- Radio-tracking may be utilised to assess specific Eastern Quoll demographics, home range and den site attributes, and the timing of and causes of mortality. It is much more sensitive than both cage trapping and camera traps and can be critical to identify causes of quoll mortality and achieve reintroduction success (Moseby et al. 2015, Moseby et al. 2021), or understand failure (Robinson et al. 2020). An area for possible standardisation is the percentage of a translocated Eastern Quoll population that should be monitored by radio-collaring to best assess survival, home ranges, dispersal and causes of mortality, noting though that this is predominantly driven by cost and available funds, and the human resources available to effectively monitor the collared quolls.

The EMSA modules that can be leveraged for this species include the [Vertebrate Fauna Module](#) (Trapping protocols) (O'Neill et al. 2023), [Camera Trapping Module](#) (Laws et al. 2024) [Signs-based Fauna Surveys](#) (Cox et al. 2023) and [Fauna Ground Counts Module](#) (McCallum et al. 2023b).

3.3.4 Northern Quoll, *Dasyurus hallucatus*

The literature review of the monitoring methods relating to the Northern Quoll (*Dasyurus hallucatus*) has identified some key points that must be considered when developing species-specific survey guidelines (TERN 2024q). These points are listed below.

- Cage trapping, camera trapping and radio-tracking are well established, highly functional and applicable methods used for monitoring the Northern Quoll.
- Camera trapping can be a cost effective and ethical option for detecting Northern Quoll. The Queensland government has guidelines in place recommending that surveys of terrestrial vertebrate fauna, where possible be conducted via camera traps rather than live capture surveys (Eyre et al. 2022).
- Optimal bait lure set up allows for clear spot pattern identification on Northern Quolls (Hohnen et al. 2013), allowing for individual identification via camera trap surveys and capture-recapture abundance studies.
- Standardisation of methodology may include spacing of cage and camera traps, noting that this is primarily driven by Northern Quoll home ranges, which can vary depending on habitat and predator abundance. Hence a 250 m spacing for cage traps may be appropriate for the Pilbara populations (Hernandez-Santin et al. 2016), whereas 20 m was used for highly abundant populations on Astell and Pobassoo Islands (Rankmore et al. 2008).
- State guidelines currently recommend different lengths of times for trapping effort (number of consecutive nights traps are opened) targeting terrestrial fauna. Western Australian guidelines recommend traps to be open seven nights (EPA 2020), the Northern Territory recommends three nights (NT EPA 2013) and Queensland four nights (Eyre et al. 2022), and this is reflected in literature with inconsistent trap nights recorded between studies. Approving a standard that finds a compromise between cost and ethical concerns and conducting robust capture-mark-recapture population assessments should be considered.
- Similarly, there is no standard for the duration of camera trapping efforts, and duration may vary depending on the complexity of the monitoring being undertaken, the season and time of year that monitoring is occurring and battery life (Meek et al. 2012, Gillespie et al. 2015). The duration of camera trap surveys of the Northern Quoll average around 25 days and are probably dictated by battery life (Gillespie et al. 2015). A standard of around 25 days for camera trap duration provides a strong confidence in presence/absence and relative abundance estimates (Gillespie et al. 2015).
- Radio-tracking is an established monitoring method to help assess specific Northern Quoll demographics, home range and den site attributes, and the timing of and causes of mortality. It is much more sensitive than both cage trapping and camera traps and can be critical to identify causes of quoll mortality and achieve reintroduction success (Moseby et al. 2015, Moseby et al. 2021). An area for possible standardisation is the percentage of a translocated Northern Quoll population that should be monitored by radio-collaring to best assess survival, home ranges, dispersal and causes of mortality, noting though that this is predominantly driven by cost and available funds, and the human resources available to effectively monitor the collared quolls.

The EMSA modules that can be leveraged for this species include the [Vertebrate Fauna Module](#) (Trapping protocols) (O'Neill et al. 2023), [Camera Trapping Module](#) (Laws et al. 2024) [Signs-based Fauna Surveys](#) (Cox et al. 2023) and [Fauna Ground Counts Module](#) (McCallum et al. 2023b).

3.3.5 Greater Bilby, *Macrotis lagotis*

The literature review of the monitoring methods relating to the Greater Bilby (*Macrotis lagotis*) has identified some key points that must be addressed when developing species specific survey guidelines (TERN 2024j). These points are listed below.

- Most population studies have focused on occupancy and range of the Greater Bilby. Their trap shyness and tendency to occupy multiple burrows make conventional abundance surveys by direct observation, including trapping, ineffective at estimating population size.
- Not all signs are the same, and sign-based surveys should discriminate between signs that are distinctive and unique that can be used to confirm the presence of Bilbies, and those that should only be used to flag potential activity.
- Combining aerial and on-ground surveys are an efficient way of conducting occupation surveys.
- Conventional trapping is not effective for capturing trap-shy Bilbies. Modified trap set ups can be effective when burrow occupancy can be confirmed. This methodology is not recommended for capture-recapture population studies but can be effective for biological studies or in translocated populations.
- Extracting DNA from scats and analysing them in conjunction with spatially explicit capture-recapture analysis is a relatively new technique that can give insight into the abundance of metapopulations. Scat samples collected from across a meta-populations range must be fresh for effective DNA extraction to be undertaken. Monitoring led by Indigenous ranger groups holding traditional knowledge can provide insight into long term occupancy and inform current monitoring zones and survey sites. On-ground survey methods have been developed with, and to utilise, Indigenous rangers' tracking skills to find signs of Bilbies and the availability of resources supporting them.

The EMSA modules that can be leveraged for this species include the [Vertebrate Fauna Module](#) (Trapping protocols) (O'Neill et al. 2023), [Camera Trapping Module](#) (Laws et al. 2024) [Signs-based Fauna Surveys](#) (Cox et al. 2023) and [Fauna Ground Counts Module](#) (McCallum et al. 2023b).

3.3.6 New Holland Mouse, Pookila, *Pseudomys novaehollandiae*

The literature review of the monitoring methods relating to the New Holland Mouse (*Pseudomys novaehollandiae*) has identified some key points that must be considered when developing species-specific survey guidelines (TERN 2024o). These points are listed below.

- Live trapping is the most common method used to determine presence of the New Holland Mouse, although hair tubes have also been employed to detect the species (Wilson and Roede 1998, Visoiu and Driessen 2018), and in more recent years camera trapping (Burns et al. 2018, Visoiu and Driessen 2018, Smith et al. 2023).
- Seasonal behaviour can influence trapping success (Burns 2019). The optimal time for trapping is early autumn as this is when the new cohort has assimilated, and population numbers are at their highest (Braithwaite and Gullan 1978, Fox and Fox 1978, Burns 2019). Males disappear for several months over summer so trapping during this period is unfavourable (Kemper 1980, Wilson et al. 2005).
- Local abundances and moon phase have been found to strongly impact detectability of the species and can reduce confidence when determining absence from a location (Burns 2019). Thus, survey effort should be increased when numbers are low and timing should coincide with a new moon where possible (Burns 2019).
- Live trapping survey effort is reported as generally more intensive than recommended by Survey guidelines for Australia's threatened mammals (DSEWPC 2011) for small-sized ground dwelling species (10-300 g weight range).
- Camera traps are an effective monitoring option particularly when non-invasive monitoring is preferred, however, it can be difficult to differentiate the New Holland Mouse from similar looking species (e.g. house mouse *Mus musculus*). To capture images that identification can be effectively obtained from, it's recommended that camera settings are set to their highest sensitivity and most surveys used bait lures around 1 to 1.5 m from the camera (Meek et al. 2015, Burns et al. 2018, Visoiu and Driessen 2018).

The EMSA modules that can be leveraged for this species include the [Vertebrate Fauna Module](#) (Trapping protocols) (O'Neill et al. 2023) and [Camera Trapping Module](#) (Laws et al. 2024).

3.3.7 Numbat, *Myrmecobius fasciatus*

The literature review of the monitoring methods relating to the Numbat (*Myrmecobius fasciatus*) has identified some key points that must be considered when developing species-specific survey guidelines (TERN 2024r). These points are listed below.

- Monitoring should target suitable habitat, with the key habitat requirements of the Numbat being the abundance of termites, a suitably open understorey for feeding interspersed with thickets, hollow logs and other fallen debris for refuge, and the presence of *Eucalyptus* species.
- Monitoring should consider Numbat diurnal activity periods. In summer, Numbats have a distinctly bimodal pattern of activity – active during the morning, activity drop between midday and late afternoon, and a second period of activity before dusk. In winter, only one period of activity lasts four to six hours from mid-morning to mid-afternoon.
- Monitoring should consider the influence of weather on Numbat activity, with the species avoiding periods of low light intensity, high relative humidity and rain.
- Annual monitoring should be undertaken at the same time each year based on the Numbat's highly synchronised seasonal pattern of reproduction and dispersal. Monitoring in early December is recommended since all young leave their maternal home range and disperse in late November or early December. Detection is therefore more likely during this period as Numbat abundance is at its highest.
- Monitoring should consider the home ranges of Numbats, ranging from approximately 25–100 ha based on seasonal variation.
- Driven transects have been the most widely used long-term monitoring method. Speeds of 15–20 km/h should be driven along vehicle tracks during peak activity hours (mornings and late afternoons/evening), with observers recording numbat sightings to determine an index of the number of observations per 100 km.
- For long-term monitoring using habitat resources and signs searches, repeat searches should be undertaken at survey sites with an array of monitoring plots that are systematically searched, with the plot chosen randomly and no plot searched twice. One or more Numbat signs in a plot during a survey is defined as a single Numbat detection at that survey site.
- Sign surveys have been found to be more successful and cost-effective than driven transects or camera trapping for detecting Numbats in the Upper Warren region in Western Australia. Using occupancy modelling, sign surveys are appropriate to investigate changes in occupancy rates over time, which could serve as a metric for long-term Numbat monitoring (Seidlitz et al. 2021).
- Camera traps may be suitable to obtain a relative abundance index (i.e. camera trap detections per trap effort), or to record observations at dawn and/or dusk at potential shelter sites, particularly if there are multiple potential shelter sites within a survey area and limited personnel. Camera traps with a wide-angle detection zone installed at a height of 25 cm are recommended for Numbat detection.

The EMSA modules that can be leveraged for this species include the [Vertebrate Fauna Module](#) (Trapping protocols) (O'Neill et al. 2023), [Camera Trapping Module](#) (Laws et al. 2024) [Signs-based Fauna Surveys](#) (Cox et al. 2023) and [Fauna Ground Counts Module](#) (McCallum et al. 2023b).

3.3.8 Southern Bent-wing Bat, *Miniopterus orianae bassanii*

The literature review of monitoring methods for the Southern Bent-wing Bat (*Miniopterus orianae bassanii*) has identified some key points that must be addressed when developing species-specific survey guidelines (TERN 2024u). These points are listed below.

- Detailing of a full risk and benefit assessment to be undertaken before implementation of any projects that may lead to disturbance of bats. This is because studies have shown that one of the lead causes of mortality is rousing from torpor due to disturbance. It is essential that any research undertaken is done so in a way that does not negatively impact the subspecies (Department of Environment 2020).
- Guidelines for pre- and post-construction monitoring at proposed windfarm sites should be further developed and regular post-construction mortality monitoring should be undertaken.
- Guidelines for monitoring bat behaviour before and after installation of antennas for radiotracking individuals should be conducted to ensure no adverse effects such as collisions. When selecting antennas and devices, those with low levels of noise should be preferences to minimise disturbance. Ongoing monitoring of noise levels should occur because of the potential for influences by unexpected sources. Within a 100 m radius of the antennas, there should be minimal electronic equipment present (van Harten *et al.* 2019).
- Inclusion of methods for sheet sampling of scats, with minimal disturbance strategies including placing sheets at cave entrances or if within the cave, placement and collection to be done after bats exit the caves for nightly foraging (Kuhne *et al.* 2022).
- Thermal video and imaging are considered more accurate, precise and efficient than manual flyout counts by observers (Brown *et al.* 2008). Efforts should go towards standard thermal imaging guidelines and long-term thermal monitoring studies to detect even small changes.
- The National Recovery Plan for the Southern Bent-wing Bat recommends that prior to surveying, efforts should be made with local governments, landowners, organisations and individuals to identify roost sites of bats in and nearby to the project area. Current studies cannot account for all bats counted in summer maternity cave exit counts, indicating that some roost locations may not yet be identified. Development of thermal imaging technology and other techniques for more regular (including annual), accurate and efficient exit counts will enable the detection of even small population changes and hopefully lead to the identification of currently unknown non-breeding caves and roost sites (TSSC 2021).
- Further research should be conducted outside of the breeding season to get more accurate population numbers at maternity sites and non-breeding sites.
- An ongoing surveillance program could determine whether the fungus responsible for White-nose syndrome (WNS) is present but not causing disease (and, therefore, of no concern), or detect it as soon as possible after introduction to Australian populations. Survey guidelines for monitoring WNS would benefit from research into cave temperatures and bat hibernating biology (Holz *et al.* 2019).

The [EMSA Vertebrate Fauna Module](#) (Acoustic and ultrasonic recording protocols) (O'Neill *et al.* 2023) can be leveraged for this species.

3.3.9 Western Ringtail Possum, *Pseudocheirus occidentalis*

The literature review of the monitoring methods relating to the Western Ringtail Possum (*Pseudocheirus occidentalis*) has identified some key points that must be addressed when developing species-specific survey guidelines (TERN 2024y). These points are listed below.

- The most commonly used method to survey Western Ringtail Possums is nocturnal spotlighting. Repeated spotlighting surveys can deliver equivalent or improved detection rates compared to extensive trapping but involves less time and effort (Wayne et al. 2005b).
- Additionally, undertaking distance sampling during spotlighting can provide a more robust and repeatable measure of population density and abundance by accounting for detection bias (de Tores et al. 2004, de Tores and Elscot 2010, Finlayson et al. 2010, Clarke 2011).
- Distance sampling can be undertaken by vehicle or by foot, depending on vegetation density and area to be covered, and environmental factors such as moon phase, cloud cover, season and time of night should be considered.
- Surveys should be carried out between October and April when the population is at its greatest and detection rates are at their highest (Wayne et al. 2005a, Wayne et al. 2005c).
- Sign-based surveys can provide a rapid, cost-effective, simple, ethical and reliable method of species detection (Wayne et al. 2005b). Furthermore, these types of survey can reduce biases associated with observer differences. For instance, scat searches can be used as an effective alternative to spotlighting to assess distribution and relative abundance (Wayne et al. 2005b, Wayne et al. 2006, Shedley and Williams 2014).
- Density estimates can be made from drey locations (Jones et al. 1994, Thompson and Thompson 2009).
- Overall, trapping offers a poor estimate of actual population size compared to spotlighting (Wayne et al. 2005b). However, capture may be necessary for studying population demographics, radio-tracking experiments and translocations. In such cases, arboreal trapping has been found to be more effective than ground trapping (Wayne et al. 2005a, Wayne et al. 2005b), or alternatively, the use of a tranquiliser dart gun provides a more feasible option for capture (Wayne et al. 2005c, Clarke 2011, Yokochi et al. 2015, Van Helden et al. 2018).

The EMSA modules that can be leveraged for this species include the [Vertebrate Fauna Module](#) (Trapping protocols) (O'Neill et al. 2023), [Camera Trapping Module](#) (Laws et al. 2024) and [Signs-based Fauna Surveys](#) (Cox et al. 2023).

3.4 Reptiles

3.4.1 Arnhem Land Gorges Skink, *Bellatorias obiri*

The literature review of the monitoring methods relating to the Arnhem Land Gorges Skink (*Bellatorias obiri*) has identified some key points that must be addressed when developing species-specific survey guidelines (TERN 2024c). These points are listed below.

- Address key gaps in the knowledge of this cryptic species, the distribution, abundance, habitat requirements and likely threats of the species.
- Development and application of specialised species-specific survey and monitoring methods are clearly needed. The results of camera trapping trials, particularly the success of using different lures to improve detectability, are likely to prove critical in developing survey protocols for the species.

The EMSA modules that can be leveraged for this species include the [Vertebrate Fauna Module](#) (Trapping protocols) (O'Neill et al. 2023), [Camera Trapping Module](#) (Laws et al. 2024) and [Signs-based Fauna Surveys](#) (Cox et al. 2023).

3.4.3 Great Desert Skink, *Liopholis kintorei*

The literature review of the monitoring methods relating to the Great Desert Skink (*Liopholis kintorei*) has identified some key points that must be addressed when developing species-specific survey guidelines (TERN 2024i). These points are listed below.

- Despite the species' expansive range, less than 100 populations are known to exist. Surveys to readily detect the species' presence within the known range must be refined to cover the extensive potential range.
- Great Desert Skinks are not readily caught in pitfall or box traps. Therefore, lack of captures from trapping surveys cannot be interpreted as an absence.
- Trapping methods, including box traps and pitfalls, are required to enable individual marking and population estimates through mark-recapture studies. Individual Great Desert Skinks do not have unique markings. Therefore, individual identification from camera trapping is not feasible to estimate population abundance.
- Innovative techniques, such as the collection of environmental samples from burrow entrances thought to be occupied by Great Desert Skinks and subsequent analysis, is one option that might prove beneficial over trapping and other sampling methods.
- Great Desert Skinks appear to have specific habitat requirements, including the need for a mosaic landscape of different aged vegetation relating to fire regimes and 50% bare ground. Modelling also suggests that they are typically detected in habitat in areas of elevation greater than 350 m and where daily temperatures above 20 °C are maintained.

The EMSA modules that can be leveraged for this species include the [Vertebrate Fauna Module](#) (Trapping protocols) (O'Neill et al. 2023), [Camera Trapping Module](#) (Laws et al. 2024) and [Signs-based Fauna Surveys](#) (Cox et al. 2023).

3.5 Plants

3.5.1 Adamson's Blown-grass, *Lachnagrostis adamsonii*

The literature review of the monitoring methods relating to Adamson's Blown-grass (*Lachnagrostis adamsonii*) did not identify key points that must be addressed when developing species-specific survey guidelines (TERN 2024a).

General plant survey best practice methods should be applied, including:

- Annual surveys for this species include permanently marked transects, targeted searches and active searches.
- Monitoring is carried out on permanently marked parallel transects spaced five metres apart and presence/absence of the species is recorded.
- Surveys are undertaken on foot within the species' flowering period (November – December).
- Seed collection and seed banking surveys are regularly undertaken. Plant tissue vouchers are collected to determine genetic diversity within and between populations to inform diverse seed collection (Glenelg Hopkings CMA 2024).
- Surveys undertaken to identify new population areas include targeted presence absence surveys for this species focus on area adjacent to saline wetlands and watercourses within the species known range.

The EMSA modules that can be leveraged for this species include the [Vertebrate Fauna Module](#) (Trapping protocols) (O'Neill et al. 2023), [Camera Trapping Module](#) (Laws et al. 2024) and [Signs-based Fauna Surveys](#) (Cox et al. 2023).

3.5.3 King Blue-grass, *Dichanthium queenslandicum*

The literature review of the monitoring methods relating to the King Blue-grass (*Dichanthium queenslandicum*) did not identify key points that must be addressed when developing species-specific survey guidelines (TERN 2024k).

- The published literature has not explicitly described survey methods for King Blue-Grass, however, projects funded under the Saving Native Species Program are focusing on developing monitoring methods for species detection.
- Monitoring should include on-ground transect surveys in 50 x 20 m plots to record species' presence/absence.
- Surveys should be undertaken early in the peak flowering season (November – December) as this coincides with post early wet season rain.
- Soil testing can also be carried out to indicate species presence.
- Seed collection may also be performed.
- There is the potential for artificial intelligence to detect species from drone imagery captured in conjunction with on-ground surveys, however, this is still in development.

The EMSA modules that can be leveraged for this species include the [Vertebrate Fauna Module](#) (Trapping protocols) (O'Neill et al. 2023), [Camera Trapping Module](#) (Laws et al. 2024) and [Signs-based Fauna Surveys](#) (Cox et al. 2023).

3.5.5 Native Guava, *Rhodomyrtus psidioides*

The literature review of the monitoring methods relating to Native Guava (*Rhodomyrtus psidioides*) has identified some key points that must be addressed when developing species-specific survey guidelines (TERN 2024b). These points are listed below.

- The survival of the species hinges on long-term and coordinated response to the impact of Myrtle Rust, determining feasible options for maintaining wild sub-populations, further research into the ecology of Native Guava and myrtle rust, and management methods; and establishing and maintaining a viable ex-situ collection for future translocations (Silcock et al. 2021).
- Monitoring of Native Guava is focused on the impact of Myrtle Rust. The reports reviewed did not appear to include all the details required to repeat the monitoring. Based on interpretation of the reviewed documents, the key attributes for monitoring include:
 - number, location and area of occupancy of sub-populations
 - number of mature, suckering and juvenile plants
 - Flowering individuals, subsequent fruit set and seed viability
 - disease incidence and disease rating for old, mature and immature leaves
 - treatment (treated/untreated sites)
 - level of impact (i.e. total tree counts (across all sites) for crown transparency in 10 % classes and tree mortality)
 - intercept and tree height (m)
 - stage of decline (e.g. dead for at least a year)
 - weather (temperature, relative humidity (RH) and dew point on an hourly basis).
- The density of weeds as a result of the loss of Native Guava trees (NSW Government 2020) and the response to threat abatement actions should also be monitored (Silcock et al. 2021).
- Myrtle Rust most typically affects growing shoots but is only intermittently active and assessment of active symptoms is not always possible (Fensham et al. 2021).
- The monitoring approach should be underpinned by the *Saving Our Species Monitoring Evaluation and Reporting: Guidelines for conservation projects* (NSW Government 2018).
- Monitoring should also be in line with the approach of the *National Action Plan for Myrtle Rust in Australia*, including documenting myrtle rust incidence, impact, resistance among plants, demographic trends and related ecological data (Makinson et al. 2020, Silcock et al. 2021).
- Ecological Field Monitoring System Australia (EMSA) standard protocols include modules for recruitment and condition that may be relevant for surveying the Native Guava.

3.5.6 Stiff Groundsel, *Senecio behrianus*

The literature review of the monitoring methods relating to the Stiff Groundsel (*Senecio behrianus*) has identified some key points that must be addressed when developing species-specific survey guidelines (TERN 2024v). These points are listed below.

- This species will be most conspicuous and identifiable during its flowering period from January to May (Walsh 1999).
- After prolonged dry conditions, this species may dieback to below ground parts and therefore populations might be best evaluated in spring following average to above average autumn and winter rainfall as less dieback would be expected under these conditions.
- Because individual plants are not easily counted, particularly in wild subpopulations, patch size, number of patches, and stem counts should be considered the primary monitoring indices for this species (Commander 2018).
- The survival and recruitment of translocated subpopulations can be assessed if individual plants are tagged for identification.
- Sites could be systematically surveyed using permanent transects (for larger populations) or monitoring plots (for smaller populations).
- Photopoint monitoring should be considered as this will compliment other methods by providing additional information about the site conditions.
- The Stiff Groundsel has specific habitat preferences and active searches for new occurrences of the species should focus on sites with suitable habitat characteristics such as periodic flooding.
- Covariates to record with population indices include evidence of grazing or trampling, presence of weeds, climate variables (e.g. temperature, precipitation), and soil moisture.

The EMSA modules that can be leveraged for this species include the [Floristics](#) (Laws et al. 2023), [Condition](#) (McCallum et al. 2023c) and [Recruitment](#) modules.

3.5.7 Waddy-wood, Waddi, *Acacia Peuce*

The literature review of the monitoring methods relating to the Waddy (*Acacia peuce*) has identified some key points that must be considered when developing species-specific survey guidelines (TERN 2024w). These points are listed below.

- The monitoring approach should be underpinned by the *National recovery plan for threatened Acacias and Ricinocarpos gloria-medii in central Australia* (Nano et al. 2007).
- Monitoring should also be in line with the approach taken by:
 - Recovery action implementation for threatened arid acacias. Distribution, monitoring and indigenous ecological knowledge of *A. peuce*, *A. undoolyana*, *A. pickardii* and *A. latzii* (Nano et al. 2008).
 - Tracking the health of Waddy Wood (*Acacia peuce*) in the Northern Territory (Nano and Ward 2013).
- The National Recovery Plan (Nano et al. 2007) concluded that the long-term survival of the Waddy depends on sustaining high adult and sapling survival rates. Achieving this involves minimising stresses on individuals at these stages and reducing disturbances during infrequent seeding recruitment events (Nano and Ward 2013). It also highlights the importance of conducting systematic population audits and continuous monitoring to assess the distribution across age classes within populations (Nano et al. 2008). Understanding whether the populations are stable or declining is essential to implement suitable measures that guarantee the species' long-term survival (Nano et al. 2008). Continuous monitoring is also essential to assess the scale of threats linked to human activities and/or unpredictable events, such as fire (Nano et al. 2008).
- Analysis of monitoring data from NT confirms that the Waddy population dynamics are extremely slow but stable, with no change in population size or structure between 2001 and 2008 (Nano et al. 2008). Based on this analysis and current threatening processes (invasive plants and herbivores) at a low level, future monitoring frequency has been recommended by Nano et al. (2008), which are listed in Appendix 2
- Geographical isolation poses a challenge in enhancing the frequency of monitoring, and often, significant, sustained rainfall, the pivotal driver of key life processes in the Waddy, constrains access to the populations (Raghu et al. 2013).
- A significant proportion of the NT population occurs within a conservation reserve, Mac Clark (*Acacia peuce*) Conservation Reserve, with all stands within the NT population fenced (Nano et al. 2007). The National Action Plan (Nano et al. 2007) recommends establishing formal protection of significant populations of Waddy in one of the two Queensland populations.
- Active searches and opportune recording may be utilised to search for novel populations, particularly within the drainage systems in the Boulia population, which presents an increased chance of spreading beyond current known stands (Nano et al. 2007).
- At each site, Andado/Mac Clark, Boulia and Birdsville, the Waddy stands as the sole tree to attain substantial size (Nano et al. 2012). This unique characteristic could allow for drone, LIDAR or similar remote sensing techniques to monitor and map these adult trees.

The EMSA modules that can be leveraged for this species include the [Floristics](#) (Laws et al. 2023), [Condition](#) (McCallum et al. 2023c) and [Opportune](#) (Bignall et al. 2023b) modules.

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5 Appendices

Appendix 1. List of the 110 priority species of the Threatened Species Action Plan for which either literature overviews or literature reviews have been prepared

Documents are available from the [EMSA Threatened Species Survey Guidelines website](#)

Common name	Species name	Literature Overview	Literature Review
Birds			
Australasian Bittern	<i>Botaurus poiciloptilus</i>		Yes
Black-eared Miner	<i>Manorina melanotis</i>		Yes
Carnaby's Cockatoo	<i>Zanda latirostris</i>		Yes
Christmas Island Goshawk	<i>Accipiter hiogaster natalis</i>	Yes	
Eastern Curlew	<i>Numenius madagascariensis</i>		
Golden-shouldered Parrot, Alwal	<i>Psephotus chrysopterygius</i>		Yes
Hooded Plover (eastern)	<i>Thinornis cucullatus cucullatus</i>		Yes
King Island Brown Thornbill	<i>Acanthiza pusilla magnirostris</i>	Yes	
King Island Scrubtit	<i>Acanthornis magna greeniana</i>		Yes
Malleefowl	<i>Leipoa ocellata</i>	Yes	
Night Parrot	<i>Pezoporus occidentalis</i>	Yes	
Noisy Scrub-bird	<i>Atrichornis clamosus</i>		Yes
Norfolk Island Green Parrot	<i>Cyanoramphus cookii</i>	Yes	
Orange-bellied Parrot	<i>Neophema chrysogaster</i>	Yes	
Plains-wanderer	<i>Pedionomus torquatus</i>		
Princess Parrot	<i>Polytelis alexandrae</i>		Yes
Red Goshawk	<i>Erythrorhynchus radiatus</i>		Yes
Red-tailed Black Cockatoo (SE)	<i>Calyptorhynchus banksii graptogyne</i>	Yes	
Regent Honeyeater	<i>Anthochaera phrygia</i>	Yes	
Swift Parrot	<i>Lathamus discolor</i>	Yes	
Western Ground Parrot, Kyloring	<i>Pezoporus flaviventris</i>	Yes	
White-throated Grasswren, Yirlinkirrkirri	<i>Amytornis woodwardi</i>	Yes	
Frogs			
Growling Grass Frog, Southern Bell Frog	<i>Litoria raniformis</i>		Yes
Kroombit Tinker Frog	<i>Taudactylus pleione</i>	Yes	
Mountain Frog	<i>Phyllorhina kundagungan</i>		Yes
Mountain-top	<i>Cophixalus monticola</i>		Yes
Southern Corroboree Frog	<i>Pseudophryne corroboree</i>	Yes	
White-bellied Frog	<i>Anstisia alba</i>	Yes	
Mammals			
Australian Sea-lion	<i>Neophoca cinerea</i>	Yes	
Brush-tailed Rock-wallaby	<i>Petrogale penicillata</i>		Yes
Central Rock-rat, Antina	<i>Zyzomys pedunculatus</i>	Yes	
Chuditch, Western Quoll	<i>Dasyurus geoffroii</i>		Yes
Eastern Quoll, Luaner	<i>Dasyurus viverrinus</i>		Yes
Gilbert's Potoroo, Ngilkat	<i>Potorous gilbertii</i>	Yes	
Greater Bilby	<i>Macrotis lagotis</i>		
Kangaroo Island Echidna	<i>Tachyglossus aculeatus multiaculeatus</i>	Yes	
Koala (Qld, NSW, ACT)	<i>Phascolarctos cinereus</i>	Yes	
Leadbeater's Possum	<i>Gymnobelideus leadbeateri</i>	Yes	
Mountain Pygmy-possum	<i>Burrhamys parvus</i>		Yes
New Holland Mouse, Pookila	<i>Pseudomys novaehollandiae</i>		Yes
Northern Brushtail Possum	<i>Trichosurus vulpecula arnhemensis</i>		Yes
Northern Hairy-nosed Wombat, Yaminon	<i>Lasiorhinus krefftii</i>	Yes	
Northern Hopping-mouse, Woorrentinta	<i>Notomys aquilo</i>	Yes	
Northern Quoll	<i>Dasyurus hallucatus</i>		Yes

Common name	Species name	Literature Overview	Literature Review
Numbat	<i>Myrmecobius fasciatus</i>		Yes
Quokka	<i>Setonix brachyurus</i>		Yes
Southern Bent-wing Bat	<i>Miniopterus orianae bassanii</i>		Yes
Spectacled Flying-fox	<i>Pteropus conspicillatus</i>	Yes	
Western Ringtail Possum	<i>Pseudocheirus occidentalis</i>		Yes
Reptiles			
Arnhem Land Gorges Skink	<i>Bellatorias obiri</i>		Yes
Bellinger River Snapping Turtle	<i>Wollumbinia georgesi</i>	Yes	
Canberra Earless Dragon	<i>Tympanocryptis lineata</i>	Yes	
Collared Delma	<i>Delma torquata</i>	Yes	
Great Desert Skink, Tjakura, Warrarna, Mulyamiji	<i>Liopholis kintorei</i>		Yes
Green Turtle	<i>Chelonia mydas</i>		Yes
Olive Ridley Turtle	<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>		Yes
Pygmy Blue-tongue Lizard	<i>Tiliqua adelaidensis</i>		Yes
Short-nosed Sea Snake	<i>Aipysurus apraefrontalis</i>	Yes	
Western Swamp Turtle	<i>Pseudemydura umbrina</i>	Yes	
Yinnietharra Rock-dragon	<i>Ctenophorus yinnietharra</i>	Yes	
Fish			
Freshwater Sawfish	<i>Pristis pristis</i>	Yes	
Grey Nurse Shark (eastern)	<i>Carcharias taurus</i>	Yes	
Maugean Skate	<i>Zearaja maugeana</i>	Yes	
Murray Hardyhead	<i>Craterocephalus fluviatilis</i>		Yes
Red Handfish	<i>Thymichthys politus</i>	Yes	
Redfin Blue-eye	<i>Scaturiginichthys vermeilipinnis</i>	Yes	
Stocky Galaxias	<i>Galaxias tantangara</i>	Yes	
Swan Galaxias	<i>Galaxias fontanus</i>	Yes	
White's Seahorse	<i>Hippocampus whitei</i>	Yes	
Invertebrates			
Ammonite Snail	<i>Ammoniropa vigens</i>	Yes	
Cauliflower Soft Coral	<i>Dendronephthya australis</i>	Yes	
Eltham Copper Butterfly	<i>Paralucia pyrodiscus lucida</i>		Yes
Giant Gippsland Earthworm	<i>Megascolides australis</i>		Yes
Glenelg Freshwater Mussel	<i>Hyridella glenelgensis</i>	Yes	
Kangaroo Island Assassin Spider	<i>Zephyrarchaea austini</i>	Yes	
Lord Howe Island Phasmid	<i>Dryococelus australis</i>	Yes	
Margaret River Burrowing Crayfish	<i>Engaewa pseudoreducta</i>	Yes	
Mount Lidgbird Charopid Land Snail	<i>Pseudocharopa ledgbirdi</i>	Yes	
Pink Underwing Moth	<i>Phylodes imperialis smithersi</i>	Yes	
Tasmanian Giant Freshwater Crayfish	<i>Astacopsis gouldi</i>		Yes
Plants			
Adamson's Blown-grass	<i>Lachnagrostis adamsonii</i>		Yes
Angle-stemmed Myrtle	<i>Gossia gonoclada</i>	Yes	
Arckaringa Daisy	<i>Olearia arckaringensis</i>	Yes	
Border Ranges Lined Fern	<i>Antrophyum austroqueenslandicum</i>	Yes	
Bulberin Nut	<i>Macadamia janseni</i>	Yes	
Carrington Falls Pomaderris	<i>Pomaderris walshii</i>	Yes	
Davies' Waxflower	<i>Phebalium daviesii</i>	Yes	
Eremophila subangustifolia	<i>Eremophila subangustifolia</i>	Yes	
Foote's Grevillea	<i>Grevillea calliantha</i>	Yes	
Forked Spyridium	<i>Spyridium furculentum</i>	Yes	
Giant Andersonia	<i>Andersonia axilliflora</i>	Yes	
Graveside Leek-orchid	<i>Prasophyllum taphanyx</i>	Yes	
Imlay Mallee	<i>Eucalyptus imlayensis</i>	Yes	
King Blue-grass	<i>Dichanthium queenslandicum</i>		Yes

Common name	Species name	Literature Overview	Literature Review
Lax Leek Orchid	<i>Prasophyllum laxum</i>	Yes	
Little Mountain Palm	<i>Lepidorrhachis mooreana</i>	Yes	
MacDonnell Ranges Cycad	<i>Macrozamia macdonnellii</i>	Yes	
Native Guava	<i>Rhodomyrtus psidioides</i>		Yes
Pimelea cremnophila	<i>Pimelea cremnophila</i>	Yes	
Pimelea venosa	<i>Pimelea venosa</i>	Yes	
Scaly-butt Mallee	<i>Eucalyptus leprophloia</i>	Yes	
Small-flowered Snottygobble	<i>Persoonia micranthera</i>	Yes	
Smooth Davidson's Plum	<i>Davidsonia johnsonii</i>	Yes	
Stiff Groundsel	<i>Senecio behrianus</i>		Yes
Stirling Range Dryandra	<i>Banksia montana</i>	Yes	
Tangled Wattle	<i>Acacia volubilis</i>	Yes	
Waddy, Waddi, Waddy-wood, Birdsville Wattle	<i>Acacia peuce</i>		Yes
Wollemi Pine	<i>Wollemia nobilis</i>	Yes	
Wongan Eriostemon	<i>Philotheca wonganensis</i>	Yes	
Woods Well Spyridium	<i>Spyridium fontis-woodi</i>	Yes	

Appendix 2. List of EPBC listed threatened species for which species-specific survey guidelines exist.

Shaded rows indicate species that have species-specific guideline recommendations in this document. Un-shaded rows indicate that species that have species-specific guideline recommendations *Survey guidelines for Australia's threatened birds* DEWHA (2010a), *Australia's threatened frogs* DEWHA (2010b), *Australia's threatened mammals* (DSEWPC 2011a), and *Australia's threatened reptiles* (DSEWPC 2011b).

EPBC Conversation status: CR Critically Endangered, EN Endangered, VU Vulnerable, EX Extinct, EX? Presumably extinct.

Species	Scientific name	EPBC conservation status	TS Action Plan Priority Species
Birds			
Australasian Bittern	<i>Botaurus poiciloptilus</i>	EN	Yes
Eastern Curlew	<i>Numenius madagascariensis</i>	CR	Yes
Hooded Plover (eastern)	<i>Thinornis cucullatus cucullatus</i>	VU	Yes
King Island Scrubtiit	<i>Acanthornis magna greeniana</i>	EN	Yes
Noisy Scrub-bird	<i>Atrichornis clamosus</i>	EN	Yes
Plains-wanderer	<i>Pedionomus torquatus</i>	CR	Yes
Abbot's booby	<i>Papasula abbotii</i>	EN	
Amsterdam albatross	<i>Diomedea amsterdamensis</i> , <i>Diomedea exulans amsterdamensis</i>	EN	
Antarctic tern (Indian Ocean)	<i>Sterna vittata vittata</i>	VU	
Antarctic tern (New Zealand)	<i>Sterna vittata bethunei</i>	EN	
Antipodean albatross	<i>Diomedea antipodensis</i> ,	VU	
Australian lesser noddy	<i>Anous tenuirostris melanops</i>	VU	
Australian painted snipe	<i>Rostratula australis</i>	VU	
Baudin's black cockatoo, long billed cockatoo	<i>Calyptorhynchus baudinii</i> ,	VU	
Black breasted button quail	<i>Turnix melanogaster</i>	VU	
Black-browed albatross	<i>Thalassarche melanophris</i> ,	VU	
Black-eared miner	<i>Manorina melanotis</i> , <i>Manorina falvigula melanotis</i>	EN	Yes
Black-throated finch (southern)	<i>Poephila cincta cincta</i>	EN	
Blue petrel	<i>Halobaena caerulea</i>	VU	
Brown thornbill (King Island)	<i>Acanthiza pusilla archibaldi</i> ,	EN	Yes
Buff-banded rail (Cocos (Keeling) Islands), Cocos Buff-banded Rail	<i>Gallirallus philippensis andrewsi</i>	EN	
Buff-breasted button quail	<i>Turnex olivei</i>	CR	
Buller's albatross, Pacific albatross	<i>Thalassarche bulleri</i>	VU	
Campbell albatross, black-browed albatross (Campbell island subsp.)	<i>Thalassarche impavida</i> , <i>Diomedea melanophris impavida</i>	VU	
Cape Barren goose (South-western)	<i>Cereopsis novaehollandiae grisea</i>	VU	
Carnaby's Black-Cockatoo	<i>Calyptorhynchus latirostris</i>	EN	Yes
Chatham albatross	<i>Thalassarche eremita</i>	EN	
Chestnut-rumped heathwren (Mount Lofty Ranges)	<i>Hylacola pyrrhopygia parkeri</i>	EN	
Christmas Island frigatebird, Andrew's Frigatebird	<i>Fregata andrewsi</i>	VU	
Christmas Island goshawk	<i>Accipiter fasciatus natalis</i>	EN	
Christmas Island hawk owl, Christmas Boobook	<i>Ninox natalis</i>	VU	
Coxen's fig parrot	<i>Cyclopsitta diophthalma coxeni</i>	CR	
Crested shrike tit (northern), Northern Shrike-tit	<i>Falculculus frontatus whitei</i>	VU	
Crimson finch (white-bellied), White-bellied Crimson Finch	<i>Neochima phaeton evangelinae</i>	VU	

Species	Scientific name	EPBC conservation status	TS Action Plan Priority Species
Eastern bristlebird	<i>Dasyornis brachypterus</i>	EN	
Emerald dove (Christmas Island), Christmas island emerald dove	<i>Chalcophaps indica natalis</i>	EN	
Fairy prion (southern)	<i>Pachyptila tutur subantarctica</i>	VU	
Forty-spotted pardalote	<i>Pardalotus quadragintus</i>	EN	
Gibson's albatross	<i>Diomedea gibsoni</i>	VU	
Glossy black cockatoo (Kangaroo Island)	<i>Calyptorhynchus lathami halmaturinus</i>	EN	
Golden whistler (Norfolk Island)	<i>Pachycephala pectoralis xanthoprocta</i>	VU	
Golden-shouldered parrot, Alwal, Thaku, Armorrall, Minpin	<i>Psephotus chrysopterygius</i>	EN	
Gouldian finch	<i>Erythrura gouldiae</i>	EN	
Gould's petrel, Australian Gould's Petrel	<i>Pterodroma leucoptera leucoptera</i>	EN	
Grey grasswren (Bulloo)	<i>Amytornis barbatus barbatus</i>	VU	
Grey-headed albatross	<i>Thalassarche chrysostoma</i>	VU	
Helmeted honeyeater, Yellow-tufted Honeyeater (Helmeted)	<i>Lichenostomus melanops cassidix</i>	CR	
Herald petrel	<i>Pterodroma heraldica</i>	CR	
Hooded robin (Tiwi Islands), Tiwi Islands Hooded Robin	<i>Melanodryas cucullata melvillensis</i>	EN	
Imperial shag (Heard Island), Heard Shag	<i>Phalacrocorax nivalis</i>	VU	
Indian yellow-nosed albatross	<i>Thalassarche carteri</i>	VU	
Island thrush (Christmas Island)	<i>Turdus poliocephalus erythropleurus</i>	EN	
Kermadec petrel (western)	<i>Pterodroma neglecta neglecta</i>	VU	
Lord Howe Island currawong, Pied Currawong (Lord Howe Island)	<i>Strepera graculina crissalis</i>	VU	
Lord Howe woodhen	<i>Hypotaenidia sylvestris</i>	VU	
Macquarie shag	<i>Phalacrocorax purpurascens</i>	VU	
Mallee emu wren	<i>Stipiturus mallee</i>	VU	
Malleefowl	<i>Leipoa ocellata</i>	VU	Yes
Masked owl (northern)	<i>Tyto novaehollandiae Kimberli</i>	VU	
Masked owl (Tiwi Islands)	<i>Tyto novaehollandiae melvillensis</i>	EN	
Night parrot	<i>Pezoporus occidentalis</i>	EN	Yes
Noisy scrub bird, Tjamiluk	<i>Atrichornis clamosus</i>	VU	
Norfolk Island Boobook, Norfolk Island Morepork, Southern Boobook (Norfolk Island)	<i>Ninox novaeseelandiae undulata</i>	EN	
Norfolk Island green parrot, Tasman Parakeet, Norfolk Island Parakeet	<i>Cyanoramphus cookie (previously C. novaezealandiae cookie)</i>	EN	Yes
Northern giant petrel	<i>Macronectes halli</i>	VU	
Northern royal albatross	<i>Diomedea sanfordi</i>	EN	
Orange-bellied parrot	<i>Neophema chrysogaster</i>	CR	Yes
Pacific albatross	<i>Thalassarche sp. nov.</i>	VU	
Painted button quail (Houtman Abrolhos)	<i>Turnix varius scintillans</i>	VU	
Partridge pigeon (eastern)	<i>Geophaps smithii smithii</i>	VU	
Partridge pigeon (western)	<i>Geophaps smithii blaauwi</i>	VU	
Princess parrot, Alexandra's Parrot	<i>Polytelis alexandrae</i>	VU	Yes
Purple-crowned fairy wren (western)	<i>Malurus coronatus coronatus</i>	EN	
Red goshawk	<i>Erythrotriorchis radiatus</i>	VU	Yes
Red-lored whistler	<i>Pachycephala rufogularis</i>	VU	
Red-tailed black cockatoo (south-eastern)	<i>Calyptorhynchus banksia graptogyne</i>	EN	Yes
Regent Honeyeater	<i>Xanthomyza phrygia</i>	CR	Yes
Regent parrot (eastern)	<i>Polytelis anthopeplus monarchoides</i>	VU	
Round Island petrel, Trinidad Petrel	<i>Pterodroma arminjoniana</i>	CR	
Salvin's albatross	<i>Thalassarche salvini</i>	VU	
Scarlet robin (Norfolk island), Norfolk Island Robin, Pacific Robin	<i>Petroica multicolor</i>	VU	

Species	Scientific name	EPBC conservation status	TS Action Plan Priority Species
Scrubtit (King Island)	<i>Acanthornis magnus greenianus</i>	CR	
Shy albatross	<i>Thalassarche cauta</i>	VU	
Soft-plumaged petrel	<i>Pterodroma mollis</i>	VU	
Sooty albatross	<i>Phoebetria fusca</i>	VU	
Southern cassowary (Australian)	<i>Casuarius casuarius johnsonii</i>	EN	
Southern emu wren (Eyre Peninsula)	<i>Stipiturus malachurus parimeda</i>	VU	
Southern emu wren (Fleurieu Peninsula)	<i>Stipiturus malachurus intermedius</i>	EN	
Southern Giant petrel	<i>Macronectes giganteus</i>	EN	
Southern royal albatross	<i>Diomedea epomophora</i>	VU	
Spotted quail thrush (Mt Lofty Ranges)	<i>Cinclosoma punctatum anachoreta</i>	CR	
Squatter pigeon (southern)	<i>Geophaps scripta scripta</i>	VU	
Star finch (eastern)	<i>Neochima ruficauda ruficauda</i>	EN	
Superb parrot	<i>Polytelis swainsonii</i>	VU	
Swift parrot	<i>Lathamus discolor</i>	CR	Yes
Thick-billed grasswren	<i>Amytornis textilis modestus</i>	VU	
Thick-billed grasswren (Gawler Ranges)	<i>Amytornis textilis myall</i>	VU	
Tristan Albatross	<i>Diomedea dabbenena</i>	EN	
Wandering Albatross, Snowy Albatross	<i>Diomedea exulans</i>	VU	
Wedge-tailed eagle (Tasmanian)	<i>Aquila audax fleayi</i>	EN	
Western bristlebird	<i>Dasyornis longirostris</i>	VU	
Western ground parrot, Kyloring	<i>Pezoporus wallicus flaviventris</i>	EN	Yes
Western whipbird (eastern), Mallee Western Whipbird	<i>Psophodes nigrogularis leucogaster</i>	VU	
Western whipbird (western heath)	<i>Psophodes nigrogularis nigrogularis</i>	EN	
Western whipbird (western mallee), Western Wheatbelt Whipbird	<i>Psophodes nigrogularis oberon</i>	VU	
White-bellied storm petrel (Tasman Sea)	<i>Fregetta grallaria grallaria</i>	VU	
White-capped albatross	<i>Thalassarche steadi</i>	VU	
Frogs			
Southern Bell Frog	<i>Litoria raniformis</i>	VU	Yes
Mountain Frog	<i>Phyllorhina kundagungan</i>	EN	Yes
Mountain-top Nursery Frog	<i>Cophixalus monticola</i>	CR	Yes
White-bellied Frog, Creek Frog	<i>Geocrinia alba</i>	CR	Yes
Orange-bellied Frog	<i>Geocrinia vitellina</i>	VU	
Giant burrowing Frog	<i>Heleioporus australiacus</i>	VU	
Green and Golden Bell Frog	<i>Litoria aurea</i>	VU	
Booroolong Frog	<i>Litoria booroolongensis</i>	EN	
Yellow-spotted Tree Frog, Yellow-spotted Bell Frog	<i>Litoria castanea</i>	CR	
Northern Heath Frog, Littlejohn's treefrog	<i>Litoria littlejohni</i>	EN	
Armoured mist frog	<i>Litoria lorica</i>	CR	
Waterfall Frog, Torrent Tree Frog	<i>Litoria nannotis</i>	EN	
Mountain mist frog, Nyakala Frog	<i>Litoria nyakalensis</i>	CR	
Wallum sedge Frog	<i>Litoria olongburensis</i>	VU	
Peppered Tree Frog	<i>Litoria piperata</i>	VU	
Common mist frog	<i>Litoria rheocola</i>	CR	
Spotted Tree Frog	<i>Litoria spenceri</i>	CR	
Alpine Tree Frog, Verreaux's Alpine Tree Frog	<i>Litoria verreauxii alpina</i>	VU	
Stuttering Frog, Southern Barred Frog	<i>Mixophyes balbus</i>	VU	
Fleay's Frog	<i>Mixophyes fleayi</i>	EN	
Giant Barred Frog, Southern Barred Frog	<i>Mixophyes iteratus</i>	VU	
Lace-eyed Tree Frog, Australian Lacelid	<i>Nyctimystes dayi</i>	VU	
Baw Baw Frog	<i>Phyllorhina frosti</i>	CR	
Southern Corroboree Frog	<i>Pseudophryne corroboree</i>	CR	Yes

Species	Scientific name	EPBC conservation status	TS Action Plan Priority Species
Magnificent Brood Frog	<i>Pseudophryne covacevichae</i>	VU	
Northern Corroboree Frog	<i>Pseudophryne pengilleyi</i>	CR	
Sunset Frog	<i>Spicospina flammocaerulea</i>	VU	
Eungella Day Frog	<i>Taudactylus eungellensis</i>	EN	
Kroombit Tinker Frog, Pleione's Torrent Frog	<i>Taudactylus Pleione</i>	CR	Yes
Tinkling Frog	<i>Taudactylus rheophilus</i>	CR	
Mammals			
Brush-tailed Rock-wallaby	<i>Petrogale penicillata</i>	VU	Yes
Chuditch, Western Quoll	<i>Dasyurus geoffroii</i>	VU	Yes
Eastern Quoll, Luaner	<i>Dasyurus viverrinus</i>	EN	Yes
Northern Quoll	<i>Dasyurus hallucatus</i>	EN	Yes
Greater Bilby	<i>Macrotis lagotis</i>	VU	Yes
New Holland Mouse, Pookila	<i>Pseudomys novaehollandiae</i>	VU	Yes
Numbat	<i>Myrmecobius fasciatus</i>	EN	Yes
Southern bent-winged bat	<i>Miniopterus schreibersii bassanii</i> (southern form)	CR	Yes
Western Ringtail Possum	<i>Pseudocheirus occidentalis</i>	CR	Yes
Arnhem Land rock rat, Kodjper	<i>Zyomys maini</i>	VU	
Banded hare wallaby	<i>Lagostrophus fasciatus fasciatus</i>	VU	
Barrow Island euro, Barrow Island Wallaroo	<i>Macropus robustus isabellinus</i>	VU	
Black-flanked rock wallaby, Mooroorong	<i>Petrogale lateralis lateralis</i>	EN	
Black-footed rock wallaby (MacDonnell Ranges), warru	<i>Petrogale lateralis centralis</i>	VU	
Black-footed rock wallaby (west Kimberly race)	<i>Petrogale lateralis kimberleyensis</i>	EN	
Boodie, burrowing bettong (Barrow and Boodie Island)	<i>Bettongia lesueur, unnamed subsp.</i>	VU	
Boodie, burrowing bettong (inland subspecies)	<i>Bettongia lesueur graii</i>	EX?	
Boodie, burrowing bettong (Shark Bay)	<i>Bettongia lesueur lesueur</i>	VU	
Bramble Cay melomys	<i>Melomys rubicola</i>	EX	
Bridled nailtail wallaby	<i>Onychogalea fraenata</i>	EN	
Brush-tailed rabbit rat, Brush-tailed tree-rat, Pakooma	<i>Conilurus penicillatus</i>	VU	
Brush-tailed rock wallaby	<i>Petrogale penicillata</i>	VU	
Carpentarian dunnart	<i>Sminthopsis butleri</i>	VU	
Carpentarian rock rat	<i>Zyomys palatalis</i>	EN	
Central rock rat, Antina	<i>Zyomys pedunculatus</i>	CR	Yes
Christmas Island shrew	<i>Crocidura attenuate trichura</i>	CR	
Dayang, heath rat, Heath mouse	<i>Pseudomys shortridgei</i>	EN	
Dibbler	<i>Parantechinus apicalis</i>	EN	
Dusky hopping mouse, wilkiniti	<i>Notomys fuscus</i>	VU	
Eastern barred bandicoot (mainland)	<i>Perameles gunnii</i> unnamed subsp.	EN	
Eastern barred bandicoot (Tasmania)	<i>Perameles gunnii gunnii</i>	VU	
Fluffy glider, yellow-bellied glider (Wet Tropics)	<i>Petaurus australis</i> unnamed subsp	EN	
Gilbert's potoroo, Ngilkat	<i>Potorous gilbertii</i>	CR	Yes
Golden bandicoot	<i>Isodon auratus auratus</i>	VU	
Golden bandicoot (Barrow Island)	<i>Isodon auratus barrowensis</i>	VU	
Greater stick-nest rat, wopilkara	<i>Leporillus conditor</i>	VU	
Hastings River mouse, Koontoo	<i>Pseudomys oralis</i>	EN	
Julia Creek dunnart	<i>Sminthopsis douglasi</i>	VU	
Kangaroo Island dunnart	<i>Sminthopsis aitkeni</i>	EN	

Species	Scientific name	EPBC conservation status	TS Action Plan Priority Species
Kowari, brushy-tailed marsupial rat, Byrne's crest-tailed marsupial rat	<i>Dasyuroides byrnei</i>	EN	
Leadbeater's possum	<i>Gymnobelideus leadbeateri</i>	CR	
Long-footed potoroo	<i>Potorous longipes</i>	VU	
Long-nosed potoroo (SE mainland)	<i>Potorous tridactylus tridactylus</i>	VU	
Mahogany glider	<i>Petaurus gracilis</i>	EN	
Mountain pygmy possum	<i>Burramys parvus</i>	EN	
Northern Bettong	<i>Bettongia tropica</i>	EN	
Northern hairy-nosed wombat	<i>Lasiorhinus krefftii</i>	CE	Yes
Northern hopping mouse, Woorentinti	<i>Notomys aquilo</i>	EN	Yes
Northern quoll, Digul [Gogo-Yimidir, Wijjingadda [Dambimangari], Wiminji [Martu]	<i>Dasyurus hallucatus</i>	EN	
Pilliga mouse, Poolkoo	<i>Pseudomys pilligaensis</i>	VU	
Plains rat, Palyoora, Plains Mouse	<i>Pseudomys australis</i>	VU	
Proserpine rock wallaby	<i>Petrogale persephone</i>	EN	
Quokka	<i>Setonix brachyurus</i>	VU	Yes
Recherche rock wallaby	<i>Petrogale lateralis hacketti</i>	VU	
Red-tailed phascogale, Red-tailed Wambenger, Kenngoor	<i>Phascogale calura</i>	VU	
Rufous hare wallaby (Bernier Island)	<i>Lagorchestes hirsutus bernieri</i>	VU	
Rufous hare wallaby (central mainland form), mala	<i>Lagorchestes hirsutus unnamed subsp.</i>	EN	
Rufous hare wallaby (Dorre Island)	<i>Lagorchestes hirsutus dorreae</i>	VU	
Sandhill dunnart	<i>Sminthopsis psammophila</i>	EN	
Shark Bay mouse, Djoongari, Alice Springs Mouse	<i>Pseudomys fieldi</i>	VU	
Smoky mouse, konoom	<i>Pseudomys fumeus</i>	EN	
Southern brown bandicoot	<i>Isoodon obesulus obesulus</i>	EN	
Southern brown bandicoot (Nyuts Archipelago)	<i>Isoodon obesulus nauticus</i>	VU	
Spectacled hare wallaby (Barrow Island)	<i>Lagorchestes conspicillatus conspicillatus</i>	VU	
Spotted-tailed quoll (North Queensland), Yarri	<i>Dasyurus maculatus gracilis</i>	EN	
Spotted-tailed quoll (southeast mainland and Tasmania), Tiger quoll, Spot-tailed quoll	<i>Dasyurus maculatus maculatus</i>	EN	
Tasmanian devil	<i>Sarcophilus harrisii</i>	EN	
Water mouse, false water rat, Yirrkoo	<i>Xeromys myoides</i>	VU	
Western barred bandicoot (Shark Bay)	<i>Perameles bougainville bougainville</i>	EN	
Western ringtail possum, Ngwayir, Womp, Woder, Ngoor, Ngoolangit	<i>Pseudocheirus occidentalis</i>	CE	Yes
Woylie, brush-tailed bettong	<i>Bettongia penicillata ogilbyi</i>	EN	
Yellow-footed rock wallaby	<i>Petrogale xanthopus xanthopus, (xanthopus celeris in Queensland)</i>	VU	
Bats			
Bare-rumped sheath tailed bat	<i>Saccolaimus saccolaimus nudicluniatus</i>	CE	
Greater large-eared horseshoe bat	<i>Rhinolophus philippinensis (large form)</i>	EN	
Semon's leaf-nosed bat, Greater Wart-nosed Horseshoe-bat	<i>Hipposideros semoni</i>	EN	
Large-eared pied bat, large-pied bat	<i>Chalinolobus dwyeri</i>	VU	
Spectacled flying fox	<i>Pteropus conspicillatus</i>	VU	
Christmas island pipistrelle	<i>Pipistrellus murrayi</i>	CR	
Grey-headed flying fox	<i>Pteropus poliocephalus</i>	VU	
South-eastern long-eared bat, Corben's Long-eared bat, Greater Long-eared bat	<i>Nyctophilus corbeni</i>	VU	
Orange leaf-nosed bat (Pilbara form), Pilbara Leaf-nosed bat	<i>Rhinonicteris aurantia</i>	VU	

Species	Scientific name	EPBC conservation status	TS Action Plan Priority Species
Reptiles			
Arnhem Land Gorges Skink	<i>Bellatorias obiri</i>	EN	Yes
Great Desert Skink, Tjakura, Warrarna, Mulyamiji	<i>Liopholis kintorei</i>	VU	Yes
Pygmy Blue-Tongue Lizard	<i>Tiliqua adelaidensis</i>	EN	Yes
Atherton delma, Legless Lizard	<i>Delma mitella</i>	VU	
Baudin Island spiny-tailed skink, Western Spiny-tailed skink	<i>Egernia stokesii aethiops</i>	EN	
Bellinger River emydura	<i>Emydura macquarii signata</i>	VU	
Blue Mountains water skink	<i>Eulamprus leuraensis</i>	EN	
Border thick-tailed gecko, Granite Belt Thick-tailed Gecko	<i>Underwoodisaurus sphyrurus</i>	VU	
Broad-headed snake	<i>Hoplocephalus bungaroides</i>	VU	
Bronzeback snake-lizard	<i>Ophidiocephalus taeniatus</i>	VU	
Christmas Island blind snake, Christmas Island Pink blind snake	<i>Typhlops exocoeti</i>	VU	
Christmas Island gecko, Lister's gecko	<i>Lepidodadectylus listeri</i>	CR	
Collared delma, Armoured delma	<i>Delma torquata</i>	VU	Yes
Corangamite water skink, Dreeite Water Skink	<i>Eulamprus tympanum marnieae</i>	EN	
Dunmall's snake	<i>Furina dunmali</i>	VU	
Fitzroy tortoise, Fitzroy River turtle, Fitzroy Turtle, White-eyed River Diver	<i>Rheodytes leukops</i>	EN	
Flinders Ranges Worm lizard	<i>Aprasia pseudopulchella</i>	VU	
Grassland Earless Dragon	<i>Tympanocryptis pinguicolla</i>	CR	
Gulf Snapping Turtle	<i>Elseya lavarackorum</i>	EN	
Hamelin ctenotus	<i>Ctenotus zassitctus</i>	VU	
Jurien Bay Skink, Jurien Bay Rock Skink	<i>Liopholis pulchra longicauda</i>	VU	
Kreffft's tiger snake	<i>Notechis scutatus ater</i>	VU	
Lancelin Island Skink	<i>Ctenotus lanceolini</i>	VU	
Long-legged worm skink, Five-clawed worm-skink	<i>Anomalopus mackayi</i>	VU	
Lord Howe Island Gecko, Lord Howe Island Southern Gecko	<i>Christinus guentheri</i>	VU	
Lord Howe Island Skink	<i>Oligosoma lichenigera</i>	VU	
Mary River Tortoise, Mary River Turtle	<i>Elusor macrurus</i>	CE	
Mount Cooper Striped Ierista, Mount Cooper Striped skink	<i>Lerista vittata</i>	VU	
Namoi River elseya	<i>Elseya belli</i>	EN	
Nangur spiny skink	<i>Nangura spinosa</i>	CE	
Olive python, Pilbara Olive Python	<i>Liasis olivaceus barroni</i>	VU	
Ornamental snake	<i>Demisonia maculata</i>	VU	
Pedra Branca skink, Pedra Branca Cool-skink, Red-Throated skink	<i>Niveoscincus palfreymani</i>	CE	
Pink-tailed worm lizard, Pink-tailed legless Lizard	<i>Aprasia parapulchella</i>	VU	
Retro slider, Allan's Ierista	<i>Lerista allanae</i>	EN	
Slater's skink, Floodplain skink	<i>Liopholis slateri slateri</i>	EN	
Striped legless lizard, Striped Snake-lizard	<i>Delma impar</i>	VU	
Three-toed snake-tooth skink	<i>Coeranoscincus reticulatus</i>	VU	
Western spiny-tailed skink, Baudin Island Spiny-tailed Skink	<i>Egernia stokesii badia</i>	EN	
Western swamp tortoise	<i>Psedemydura umbrina</i>	CR	Yes
Yakka skink	<i>Egernia rugosa</i>	VU	
Yellow-snouted Gecko, yellow snouted Ground Gecko	<i>Lucasium occultum</i>	EN	

Species	Scientific name	EPBC conservation status	TS Action Plan Priority Species
Yinnietharra rock dragon	<i>Ctenophorus yinnietharra</i>	VU	Yes
Fish			
Golden galaxias	<i>Galaxias auratus</i>	EN	
Swan galaxias	<i>Galaxias fontanus</i>	EN	Yes
Barred galaxias	<i>Galaxias fuscus</i>	EN	
Clarence galaxias	<i>Galaxias johnstoni</i>	EN	
Arthurs galaxias	<i>Paragalaxias mesotes</i>	EN	
Swamp galaxias	<i>Galaxias parvus</i>	VU	
Pedder galaxias	<i>Galaxias pedderensis</i>	EN	
Saddled galaxias	<i>Galaxias tancycephalus</i>	VU	
Western trout galaxias, Spotted galaxias, spotted mountain trout, mountain trout, spotted mountain trout	<i>Galaxias truttaceus hesperius</i>	CR	
Eastern dwarf galaxias, dwarf galaxias, dwarf minnow, eastern little galaxias, striped galaxias	<i>Galaxiella pusilla</i>	EN	
Shannon Galaxias	<i>Paragalaxias dissimilis</i>	VU	
Great lake galaxias, Greater lake darter	<i>Paragalaxias eleotroides</i>	VU	
Elizabeth Springs goby	<i>Chlamydogobius micropterus</i>	EN	
Edgbaston goby	<i>Chlamydogobius squamigenus</i>	VU	
Redfin blue-eye	<i>Scaturiginichthys vermeilipinnis</i>	EN	Yes
Murray hardyhead	<i>Craterocephalus fluviatilis</i>	EN	Yes
Flinders Ranges Gudgeon	<i>Mogurnda clivicola</i>	EN	
Balston's Pygmy Perch	<i>Nannatherina balstoni</i>	VU	
Yarra pygmy perch	<i>Nannoperca obscura</i>	EN	
Oxleyan pygmy perch	<i>Nannoperca oxleyana</i>	EN	
Variiegated pygmy perch	<i>Nannoperca variegata</i>	VU	
Australian grayling	<i>Prototroctes maraena</i>	VU	
Blind gudgeon	<i>Milyeringa veritas</i>	VU	
Blind Cave Eel	<i>Ophisternon candidum</i>	VU	
Lake Eacham rainbowfish	<i>Melanotaenia eachamensis</i>	EN	
Honey blue-eye	<i>Pseudomugil mellis</i>	EN	
Eastern Freshwater Cod	<i>Maccullochella ikei</i>	EN	
Trout Cod	<i>Maccullochella macquariensis</i>	EN	
Mary River Cod	<i>Maccullochella peelii</i>	EN	
Macquarie Perch	<i>Macquaria australasica</i>	EN	
Australian Lungfish	<i>Neoceratodus forsteri</i>	VU	
Murray Cod	<i>Maccullochella peelii</i>	VU	
Spotted Handfish	<i>Brachionichthys hirsutus</i>	CE	
Ziebell's Handfish	<i>Brachiopsilus ziebelli</i>	VU	
Red Handfish	<i>Thymichthys politus</i>	CE	Yes
Northern River Shark	<i>Glyphis garricki</i>	EN	
Spear-tooth Shark	<i>Glyphis glyphis</i>	CR	
Dwarf Sawfish	<i>Pristis clavata</i>	VU	
Freshwater Sawfish	<i>Pristis microdon</i>	VU	Yes
Green Sawfish, Dindagubba	<i>Pristis zijsron</i>	VU	
Great white shark	<i>Carcharodon carcharias</i>	VU	
Grey Nurse Shark	<i>Carcharias taurus</i>	EN	Yes
Whale shark, Checkerboard shark	<i>Rhincodon typus</i>	VU	
Maugean skate, Port Davey skate	<i>Zearaja maugeana</i>	EN	Yes
Plants			
Adamson's Blown-grass	<i>Lachnagrostis adamsonii</i>	EN	Yes
King Blue-grass	<i>Dichanthium queenslandicum</i>	EN	Yes
Native Guava	<i>Rhodomyrtus psidioides</i>	CR	Yes

Species	Scientific name	EPBC conservation status	TS Action Plan Priority Species
Stiff Groundsel	<i>Senecio behrianus</i>	EN	Yes
Waddy-wood, Waddy	<i>Acacia peuce</i>	VU	Yes

Priority threatened species listed in the Threatened Species Action Plan, for which no species-specific survey guidelines have been developed in the threatened species guidelines (2011-2012) documents, or this document (literature overviews/literature reviews of monitoring methods are available for these species .

Species	Scientific name	EPBC conservation status	TS Action Plan Priority Species
White-throated Grasswren, Yirlinkirkirri	<i>Amytornis woodwardi</i>	VU	Yes
Australian Sea-lion	<i>Neophoca cinerea</i>	EN	Yes
Kangaroo Island Echidna	<i>Tachyglossus aculeatus multiaculeatus</i>	EN	Yes
Koala (Qld, NSW, ACT)	<i>Phascolarctos cinereus</i>	E* (Qld, NSW, ACT)	Yes
Northern Brushtail Possum	<i>Trichosurus vulpecula arnhemensis</i>	VU	Yes
Spectacled Flying-fox	<i>Pteropus conspicillatus</i>	EN	Yes
Bellinger River Snapping Turtle	<i>Myuchelys georgesii</i>	CR	Yes
Canberra Earless Dragon	<i>Tympanocryptis lineata</i>	CR	Yes
Green Turtle	<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	VU	Yes
Short-nosed Sea Snake	<i>Aipysurus apraefrontalis</i>	CR	Yes
Olive Ridley Turtle	<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	EN	Yes
Stocky Galaxias	<i>Galaxias tantangara</i>	CR	Yes
White's Seahorse	<i>Hippocampus whitei</i>	EN	Yes

Appendix 3. Description of the Ecological Monitoring System of Australia (EMSA) modules

EMSA Manuals and sample datasheets available from the [EMSA website](#). The EMSA app, Monitor, supports in-field electronic data collection of these modules.

Module name	Module description
Basal area	Records basal area within plots where there is a dominant growth form of trees, shrubs and/or mallee greater than 2 m in height. An enhanced diameter at breast height (DBH), standard DBH or basal wedge protocol may be used. Data captured includes the species name, tree details, number of trees that are wider than the aperture of the basal area factor etc.
Camera trapping	Covers three camera trapping protocols (deployment, re-equipping and retrieval). Camera traps can be deployed at one or more features of interest, or in an array (i.e., grid or transect) or a fauna plot. Data captured includes survey type, camera trap make, model and settings, camera trap location and orientation, focal point, target species if applicable, bait station details, deployment period etc.
Coarse woody debris	This module covers procedures and guidelines to record coarse woody debris (CWD) length, diameter and decay class in the plot, using either a standard or enhanced protocol. Data captured includes plot size, CWD measurements and decay class.
Condition	Records biodiversity condition of the plot using a combination of point and plot-based methods. Data is collected on plant age class structure, plant health and size, litter depth, coarse woody debris and recruitment. Data from other modules also provide important measures for overall assessment of condition. Data captured includes a tree survey (diameter at breast height, species name, growth stage etc.), leaf litter depth, grazing damage etc.
Cover	Records vegetation and substrate cover within the plot using the point-intercept method with either a standard or enhanced protocol. Data captured includes substrate type, species occurrence and abundance, growth form, and height.
Fauna aerial surveys	Record fauna observations during an aerial survey from a manned aircraft. Data captured includes aircraft and model, observers, altitude, transect length, species, number, distance observed etc.
Fauna ground counts	Direct counts of fauna using transects or vantage point protocols. The module is designed for monitoring pest fauna species, but can be used on all fauna species. It may be combined with other fauna monitoring modules to estimate abundance and assess impacts of fauna species. Data captured includes date, time, location and count of observed fauna species, distance from the observer and optional details such as age class.
Fire severity	Records fire severity within the plot by recording cover and height of fire severity attributes from the ground to the canopy (at 404 point-intercepts along four 100 m transects within the plot), and trunk char height at four locations within the plot. Data captured includes fire ignition date, substrate, vascular plant information, resprouting etc.
Floristics	Record flora species composition in the plot using either a standard or enhanced protocol. Vouchers of some or all species in the plot must be collected and sent to a state or territory herbarium. All vouchers are barcoded and linked to the species ID in the Monitor app. Data captured includes field name, growth forms and vouchers (physical and photo).
Herbivory and physical damage	Record herbivory and physical damage from vertebrate fauna using up to 3 protocols (within-plot belt transect, off-plot belt transect, active plot search). The module is designed for monitoring pest fauna species, but can be used on all fauna species. It may be combined with other fauna monitoring modules to estimate abundance and assess impacts of fauna species. Depending on protocols completed, data captured can include: presence or absence of damage type, count of damage, age of the damage etc.
Invertebrate fauna	This module includes 5 field sampling protocols for terrestrial invertebrates (active search, wet pitfall trapping, rapid ground trapping, pan trapping and malaise trapping) and a post-field sample curation protocol. Invertebrates are collected and preserved to future-proof data and enable future identification. Depending on protocols completed, data captured can include: search time, weather, collection apparatus, trap location, photos, vouchers etc.
Opportune	Records opportune observations of flora (vascular and non-vascular) and fauna (vertebrate and invertebrate). Opportune observations are unplanned (no defined survey effort) and made while undertaking other activities, at any stage of a project. Observations often occur while travelling between plots and while undertaking other modules. Data collected includes date, time, location, species ID, number of individuals location, habitat, optional vouchers etc.
Pest fauna control activities	Includes pest fauna removal activities such as shooting, baiting, trapping and mustering. This module records the number of target animals removed or bait taken to monitor pest

	fauna abundance. Data captured includes target species, control method, survey effort, weather conditions etc.
Photopoints	Establishes 3 photopoints around the plot's centre, using one of three protocols (DSLR camera panorama, compact camera panorama, device camera panorama). Data collected includes plot ID and 360 degree panoramas from three points around the plot centre.
Plant tissue vouchering	Procedures and guidelines for collecting, drying and storing plant tissue vouchers within a plot using either a standard or enhanced protocol. All samples collected are barcoded, linking the voucher to the species. Data captured includes species field name, barcode ID and growth forms.
Plot Description	Describe the landform, land surface and vegetation of a plot using either a standard or enhanced protocol. Information recorded includes landform, slope and aspect, lithology, disturbance, fire history and vegetation type. Data collected includes slope, aspect, lithology, growth stage, fire history, site disturbance etc.
Plot selection and layout	This module includes procedures and guidelines for a desktop assessment of the project area and proposed plot locations, selection of plot locations in the field and marking out the plots. Plot types include the core monitoring plot and an optional paired fauna plot (both 100 x 100 m; 1 ha). Plot selection is a preliminary requirement for most modules. Data collected includes the plot layout and type.
Recruitment	This module includes 2 protocols for recording age class structure and survivorship of vegetation within the plot. Data captured includes actual count of individuals, life stage (seedling, flowering, fruiting, seeding, senescent etc.) and can also include tagging of individuals for ongoing monitoring of survivorship.
Sign-based fauna surveys	Record fauna signs in the project area using up to 5 protocols (within-plot belt transect, off-plot belt transect, plot sign search, vehicle tracks and track stations). The module is designed for monitoring pest fauna species, but can be used on all fauna species. It may be combined with other fauna monitoring modules to estimate abundance and assess impacts of fauna species. Depending on protocols completed, data captured can include: sign presence or absence, sign details, photos etc.
Soils	This module includes 4 soil protocols: soil sub-pit and metagenomics (standard or enhanced protocol), sample pit, site observation and pit characterisation and bulk density. Depending on protocols completed, data captured can include: sample location and photos, soil horizon detail, soil classification etc.
Targeted surveys	Collections metadata of surveys conducted recording an overview of the monitoring type, the scale of the monitoring, the landscapes, target species/communities, records the type of data the monitoring captured, identified data custodian contact details, and where the data is accessible from.
Vegetation mapping	Classify vegetation at precise points across the project area. Collect structural and floristic data within homogeneous vegetation that is representative of vegetation associations. Data collected includes homogeneity measure, photo, percentage cover, growth stage, fire history, disturbance etc.
Vertebrate fauna	Survey for vertebrate fauna species present within the plot using up to 5 survey protocols: trapping survey set-up and closure (standard or enhanced protocol), identify, measure and release, bird survey, active and passive search, and acoustic and ultrasonic recordings. Surveys can be completed either as trapping or non-trapping surveys. Any vouchering must be conducted under guidance from the state/territory jurisdictional museum (module does not include protocols for vouchering). Depending on protocols completed, data captured can include: trap specifications, trap success rate, species observed and population demographics, recapture of individuals, call files etc.

Appendix 4.**Checklist of Survey Information to Record**

This is not a datasheet but a list of survey-relevant metadata that is recommended to be recorded for all surveys, regardless of the species of interest or the type of monitoring being conducted. The checklist is particularly useful for monitoring projects not using the Ecological Monitoring System Australia (EMSA), or the Monitor app for data collection.

Personnel details

For each survey participant, record:

- Full name
- Associated organisation
- Experience surveying the target taxa, or similar taxa (few sentences)
- Experience surveying the survey area (few sentences)
- Role in the survey (key observer, data recorder)
- Relevant permits held (also recorded in the Permits and Authorities section)

Monitoring summary

Provide a summary of the type of monitoring being undertaken. The EMSA Targeted Surveys Module can provide some guidance. Record:

- Overview of the monitoring type, e.g. flora monitoring, fauna monitoring, habitat condition, ecological community assessment, ecological community condition, or land/soil monitoring
- Overview of the monitoring scale, e.g. state-wide, NRM region, IBRA region, IBRA sub-region, site
- Landscape of the monitoring, e.g. terrestrial, coastal, riparian/riverine, wetlands, marine, or other - describe
- Indicate the target category, e.g. vascular flora, non-vascular flora, vegetation community, birds, mammals, reptiles, frogs, invertebrates
- Specify target species or community (if applicable)
- Indicate the types of data captured – for flora, indicate what was recorded, e.g. observations, species, count of individuals, marked individuals identification number, height, diameter at breast height, stem width, canopy width, condition and health information, reproductive status, age class, indicate if samples or specimens are collected, if photos are taken, and describe any other information collected relevant to the species of interest.
- Indicate the types of data captured – for fauna, indicate what was recorded, e.g. observations, species, count of individuals, marked individuals identification number, body weight, body measures, condition and health information, sex, reproductive status, age class, indicate if samples or specimens are collected, if photos are taken, if animals are fitted with any monitoring devices (i.e. a radio-collar), and describe any other information collected relevant to the species of interest.

Methods employed

Provide a summary of the methods employed. The EMSA Targeted Surveys Module can provide some guidance. Record:

- For observations, record how observations were made, e.g. details of general wanders/meanders (duration, route details, where the observers were looking), transects (length, width, layout), quadrats or plots (area and dimensions, and proximity to other plots)
- For flora observations, record how observations were made, e.g. species presence recorded, individuals counted, individuals marked, diameter measured, canopy width measured, phenology recorded, specimen collected
- For fauna observations, record how observations were made, e.g. if conducting a bird survey, list the number of surveyors, the equipment used, if call-play back was used (if so, what species, call type was played)

- For active searches, record duration, number of observers, and typical activity (e.g. were observers lifting rocks – if so, all rocks, or a subset, and how was the subset determined, sifting through leaf litter, lifting bark, etc), and include what equipment was used
- For trapping, record all details of the traps used (e.g. dimensions, mechanism, bait type), location, trap array information (including distances between traps), trap effort (e.g. how many nights were traps used for, were they open all day and night).

Survey conditions

Note the weather conditions encountered during the survey. For each key time interval (i.e. you may need to re-record every few hours), record:

- Temperature (e.g. closet BOM weather station or field weather station/gauge you may have)
- Cloud cover (e.g. clear, mostly clear, partly cloudy, cloudy, overcast)
- Rainfall (e.g. showers, rain, drizzle, frost, mist, thunderstorms)
- Rainfall duration (e.g. intermittent, occasional, frequent, continuous, periods of rain, brief)
- Wind direction (e.g. calm, light winds, moderate winds, fresh winds, strong winds, near gale, gale)
- Wind speed
- Conditions leading up to the survey
 - For example, note if the three months prior have been exceptionally dry, wet, or average. Also note the immediate conditions if they may be relevant, i.e. if it's the first warm day after a week of colder weather. Whilst metrological records can be cross-checked at the time of the survey, a brief description of the conditions leading up to the survey can be a quick reference point.
- Moon phase (e.g. new moon, first quarter, full moon, third quarter)

Survey visit and survey effort

For each survey visit (i.e. a survey interval that forms part of the monitoring, as a minimum daily), record:

- Start date
- Start time
- End date
- End time
- Total duration (ideally to hours, or minutes for shorter surveys)
- Number of surveyors (distinguishing active survey participants and data entry only participants if relevant)

- Visit type – note if the visit is for a reconnaissance survey to scope out the survey area, an initial visit to commence basic survey techniques, the core part of the monitoring, or follow-up revisit to check anything missed/additional observations at a different time of day etc
- Timing appropriateness – record information to justify the timing of the survey. For example, is it the correct time of year, season, seasonal conditions, time of day and weather conditions to be able to observe the species of interest?
- Survey frequency – indicate the frequency of the surveys, e.g. weekly, monthly, bi-annual.

Permits, licenses and land permissions

Ensure the correct permits, ethics, and land permissions have been obtained prior to surveying, and ensure all relevant information is documented and conditions are understood. Record:

- Issuing authority
- Permit name
- Permit holder name
- Permit number
- Permit start date
- Permit expiry date
- Specified location information
- Contact details of the landholder/manager, with documented approval

Survey location

Ensure that the location of the survey area is recorded accurately. Record:

- Location coordinates
- Coordinate system
- Location accuracy to metres
- Location method (i.e. GNSS, DGPS, GPS, mobile phone/tablet device, other, none)
- Location description – sentence or two about the location, including distances for road intersections etc.

Site description

Depending on the species of interest and habitat, record information to describe the survey site. The EMSA Plot Description Module can provide some guidance. Record:

- Landform pattern and landform element
- Soils and geology
- Slope and aspect
- Lithology of any outcrops
- Lithology of any surface fragments and size
- Lithology and any further details of key habitat refuge elements important to the target species (including the abundance/frequency of suitable refuges, and absence of suitable refuges)
- Site disturbances – including erosion type, weeds, fire, clearance, rubbish

- Land use history
- Fire history, and any fire-related information that may be important to the target species

Vegetation association information

Ensure the major vegetation group, or even better the vegetation association, has been effectively described – this is applicable to all ecological surveys. The EMSA Vegetation Mapping Module provides some guidance. Record:

- Major vegetation group (examples include Rainforest and Vine Thickets, Eucalypt Tall Open Forests, Eucalypt Woodlands, Acacia Open Woodlands, Mallee Woodlands and Shrublands, Heathlands and Chenopod Shrublands). A full list is available in the EMSA Opportune Module.
- Vegetation association (to the best NVIS level description you can manage/feel appropriate)
- Dominant overstorey species, growth form, and average height, estimated foliage projective cover
- Dominant mid-storey species, growth form, and average height, estimated foliage projective cover
- Dominant understorey species, growth form, and average height, estimated foliage projective cover
- Height of the tallest stratum
- Weed/invasives abundance

Floristics

Depending on the species of interest, detailed information on the floristics of the survey area may be beneficial. Record:

- List all flora species present within the survey area, and for each species, record the growth form (tree, shrub, forb etc.) and key phenology stage present, particularly if flowering and seeding. The EMSA Floristics Module provides some guidance.

Photopoints

Take photos of your survey site for visual reference. The EMSA Photopoints Module provides some guidance.

- Take a series of photos that best represent the overall habitat, vegetation, and overall landform of the survey area. Landscape photos (not portrait) are best
- Consider taking a series of 360° panoramas from 3 points in the centre of the survey location following the guidance in the EMSA Photopoints Module.

Observation methods

Depending on your target species, and taxa type, record how observations were made. Record:

- Broad observation methods (for example, seen, signs, captured)
- More detailed observation methods (for example, seen whilst spotlighting, seen via remote camera, seen via helicopter, signs – scats, tracks, hair, wallows, captured – hand capture, pitfall trap, cage trap, Malaise trap, sweep net, etc.). A full list is available in the EMSA Opportune Module.

Observations recorded

For each observation made, note what information will be collected. Record:

- Presence/absence or non-detection, count – estimate, count – actual, abundance or frequency, cover estimates, or cover – actual (describe how cover was calculated)
- Identify if absences will be recorded
- Measurements of individuals (i.e. morphology and taxonomic measurements recorded)
- Age-class of fauna individuals (i.e. if individuals observed are assigned an age class, e.g. adult, immature, juvenile, larvae, etc)
- Clinical samples of individuals (i.e. if swabs are taken)

Observational equipment

For each item of key equipment used, record:

- Make, model and technical specifications – for items such as binoculars, scopes, thermal scopes, camera traps, acoustic recorders
- For camera traps and acoustic recorders, also include all relevant setting information, as well as the specific location of the devices (location coordinates), heights and angles set at, micro-habitat information of the immediate area, the number of devices used, and the arrangement (including spacing between devices)

Species verifications

Include information on how you established species verifications. This may apply to the species of interest, the habitat/vegetation association information, or any other plant/animal species monitoring as part of the project. Record:

- If species were identified by the surveyor using their experience, reference guides
- If vouchers were taken, and if so, where are they to be deposited—herbaria/museum, etc.? Also, note voucher numbers and voucher type (herbarium voucher, leaf tissue voucher, whole animal, animal tissue).

Data availability

To ensure awareness of the dataset and potentially enable access and re-use of the data, ensure to record:

- How data was collected (i.e. specialised app, hard copy data sheet, field notebook)
- Where data will be stored (i.e. which database will the data be provided to)
- Dataset title, and identify if there are any additional linked datasets of relevance
- Where data will be stored (i.e. which database will the data be provided to)
- Data custodian and contact details
- Important restrictions of the data, including sensitivities and applicable embargoes

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